

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project “Into-DIALOGUE”

Deliverable 2.1

**Comprehensive literature review on existing
data**

Version 1.0

Due date of deliverable: M43 (August 2023)

Actual submission date (Version 1.0) (31-03-2024)

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695
 Project acronym: EJP SOIL
 Programme title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils
 Programme website: www.ejpsoil.eu
 Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020
 Project duration: 60 months
 Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1
 Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

Project title: More than a Dialogue between actors, seeking the integration of soil-based principles in agroecological systems [Into-DIALOGUE]
 Project website: <https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/eom4soil/into-dialogue>
 Coordinator: Sabina Asins-Velis (CSIC - Spain); Co-Coordinator: Akin Ün (TAGEM - Türkiye)

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	D2.1
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	Comprehensive literature review on existing data on the basic soil properties in order to implement sustainable agricultural practices
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Report
WORK PACKAGE NUMBER:	WP2
WP LEADERS:	Anita Maienza (CNR) and Jerzy Grabinski (IUNG)
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	Farmers vision on soil properties and soil management practices to achieve sustainable agroecological systems
TASK NUMBER	2.1
TASK TITLE:	To select indicators for the characterization of the attributes that can affect the application of soil-based agroecological measures

TASK LEADERS: Martin Pisarčik (CZU) and Erica Lumini (CNR)

TEAM: Martin Pisarčik - CZU, Michelle Kushnir – CZU, Monika Vilkiene – LAMMC, Ieva Mockeviciene – LAMMC, Gabriele Buttafuoco – CNR, Anita Maienza -CNR, Erica Lumini – CNR, Baiba Dirnena – UL, Gherardo Biancofiore-CNR, Sara Di Lonardo – CNR, Sabina Asins-Velis – CSIC, Javier Renovell – CSIC, Akin Ün – TAGEM, Saddam Kalkan – TAGEM

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14169603>

LICENSE CC BY 4.0

DISSEMINATION LEVEL: PU

How to cite this report:

Pisarčik, M., Kushnir, M., Vilkiene, M., Mockeviciene, I., Buttafuoco, G., Maienza, A., Lumini, E., Dirnena, B., Biancofiore, Gh., Di Lonardo, S., Asins-Velis, S., Renovell, J., Ün, A., Kalkan, S. 2024. Comprehensive literature review on existing data on the basic soil properties in order to implement sustainable agricultural practices. Report of Into-DIALOGUE project (EJP-Soil). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14169603>.

Table of Content

1. INTRODUCTION	7
Soil quality indicators	8
Chemical properties.....	10
Soil organic matter (SOM)/ soil organic carbon (SOC)	10
Humic substances (HS)	11
Cation exchange capacity (CEC).....	12
pH.....	12
Micro and Macronutrients.....	13
Physical properties	14
Soil aggregate stability (SAS).....	14
Bulk density (BD).....	14
Biological indicators	15
Macro fauna: Earthworms	17
Mesofauna: Microarthropods.....	18
Microfauna: Nematodes.....	18
Microorganisms (Fungi-Bacteria and Virus)	19
Bacteria	19
Fungi and Mycorrhiza	20
Viruses	20
Functional Indicators:	21
Enzyme activities	21
Microbial Carbon Biomass (MCB/Cmic)	21
Soil Respiration (SR).....	21
Agroecological practices	21
Tillage.....	23
Mineral Fertilization.....	23
Organic Amendment.....	24
Cover Crops	25
2. METHODOLOGY	27
Study protocol.....	27
Query Items and screening process	28
Data Analysis	30
3. RESULTS	33
General Results.....	33

Climate	33
Agronomic Practices.....	¡Error! Marcador no definido.
Crops.....	36
Soil.....	37
Soil Texture	37
Soil properties.....	37
Effect of agroecological practices on soil indicators.....	38
4. DISCUSSION	41
5. CONCLUSIONS	43
6. REFERENCES.....	44

Figure List

Figure 1.1. Soil type map of European continent. (EC, 2005)	8
Figure 1.2. Frequency of different indicators (min. 10%) in all reviewed soil quality assessment approaches (n = 65) (Bünemann et al., 2018).....	10
Figure 1.3. Groups of humic substances according to method EN ISO 19822 (Piribauer et al., 2020).	12
Figure 1.4. Some biogeochemical processes and their relations with soil pH (by Neina D., 2019) .	13
Figure 1.5. Schematic composition of soil aggregates (Schlüter et al., 2018)	14
Figure 1.6. Linkage between soil biological indicators and environmental variables (SOIL BON program Guerra et al., 2021)	16
Figure 1.7. Trophic and engineering interactions among soil organisms (Briones, 2014).....	17
Figure 1.8. Impact on long-term chemical and organic-only fertilization on soil microbial communities (Xu et al., 2020).	20
Figure 2.1. The methodology involved studying results on literature.....	27
Figure 3.1. The total number of papers analyzed for review in Into Dialogue task 2.1	33
Figure 3.2. The Environmental Stratification of Europe proposed by Metzger (2005)	34
Figure 3.3. The main agronomic practices studied in the paper were analyzed in the review.....	35
Figure 3.4. % of Agronomic practices divided for country.....	36
Figure 3.5. The main crops object of Long-Term experiment investigates with the review.....	36
Figure 3.6. % of total soil texture	37
Figure 3.7. The main soil properties resulted object of study in the review.	38
Figure 3.8. Effect of soil agroecological practices analyzed on soil quality indicators.	39
Figure 3.9. Heatmap on effect of practices on soil parametes.....	39
Figure 3.10. Discriminant analysis on the effect vs enviromentals zone.	40

Table List

Table 1.1. Based on data reported in Stolte et al. (2015), Gregory et al. (2015). Created by Lorenz et al. (2019).....	11
Table 1.2. Examples of presumed impacts of increase in organic matter content by 1% on soil water retention (Lal, 2020)	15
Table 2.1. Summary of the results obtained with the Query of the systematic review	29
Table 2.2. Number of Analyzed Papers by Country.....	30
Table 2.3. categories of indicator of ecosystem services	32

1. Introduction

The present report provides some insights into the assessments of relations between agroecological practices and soil quality available in literature of seven participating countries (Italy, Poland, Spain, Czech Republic, Latvia, Lithuania and Turkey) in the Into-DIALOGUE project. The focus is on the response of soil quality parameters (and related soil ecosystem services) most frequently investigated within literature, in Long Term Field Experiments, in relation to agroecological practices in each country.

“Soil is vital for living things. It is one of the most basic resources for life. However, being subject to intense pressure due to human activities, it is continuing to become less productive day by day. These increasing pressures and threats have forced stakeholders to take serious measures for soil sustainability.” - Milestone 4.2 Into Dialogue

The research objectives being addressed through this systematic literature review consisted of to consolidate the existing literature and identify thematic areas in the literature in agroecological practices and soil quality. Also, to identify the gaps in existing literature and define the potential focus areas for future researchers in the field of soil science. Soil was generally underestimated by society during the last century. Soils consist naturally of 4 parts – water, air, organic matter and minerals (Young, 2012), which mostly influences soil physical and chemical properties. Besides visual assessment approaches to soil quality (Bünemann et al., 2018) scientists and farmers use analytical approaches to measure soil properties.

According to mineral composition, amount and origin is distinguished into several soil types. This classification was first created by Dokutschajew in 1870s and the scientific field of pedology developed from that time (Rusakova et al., 2022).

“A nation that destroys its soils destroys itself.” - Franklin Delano Roosevelt

Into-DIALOGUE countries vary between each other and therefore it is needed to characterise soil properties among them:

Lithuania and Poland are represented by Albeluvisols, Cambisols, Phaeozems, Podzols and Luvisols respectively. Albeluvisols and Acrisols are extremely acidic soils with a low base saturation (<35%) and a high concentration of exchangeable aluminium, with clay accumulation in the subsurface horizons composed of kaolinitic clay mineralogy (low cation exchange capacity and pH-dependent charge), and with a high Fe and Al oxide and oxyhydroxide content. If taken together all these properties, these soils are generally considered having very low capacity for agricultural use. If these soils are to be used for agriculture, they require organic amendments and lime treatment to increase the pH, which enables controlling the Al³⁺ toxicity (generally saturated above the 60% capacity value for sensitive crops), and the availability of P (adsorption is related to Fe oxides, Al³⁺ Mn, and amorphous or weakly crystalline aluminosilicate). Podzols are highly acidic, display low fertility, have an excessive permeability of the eluvial (leaching process) horizon, and sometimes are characterized by a cementation of the subsurface cambic horizon. Because of all these properties, the

most frequent land use of these soils is forestry. Latvia soils shows high diversity in geological deposits and moisture conditions (Kasparinskis & Nikodemus, 2012; Nikodemus et al., 2013). According to WRB classification in central Latvia lowland most of soils corresponds to Phaeozems or Stagnosols. However, in uplands predominates Luvisols, Cambisols, Gleysols and Histosols. Due to changes in soil texture and moisture conditions, as well as undulated topography in uplands soil contours are relatively small in Latvia. Therefore, for characterization of soil distribution in many cases are used soil associations. Characteristic soil association in glacial till upland is following: Luvisols, Arenosols, Stagnosols in slopes and crest of topography, but in lower part of slopes – Gleysols and in depression valleys – Histosols. In dunes soil association is formed by Arenosols, Cambisols, Podzols and Histosols. In central Latvia lowland (Zemgales plain) the soil types distributed are Phaeozems or Stagnosols as well as Cambisols and Luvisols (Figure 1.1).

Czech Republic, Italy and Spain have in common most of their territory covered by Cambisols (Figure 1.1). Particular soils in lowland areas such as Elbe and Morava lowlands including Chernosols and Luvisols; and in mountain areas, especially surrounding country, illimerized soils and Podzols can be found (Kozák et al., 2003). When added to Calcisols and Leptosols, these are also the most abundant soils in **Turkey**. More than half of the territory in Spain is dominated by lime and calcareous rocks including clays, characterized by calcareous Cambisol and haplic Cambisol.

Figure 1.1. Map of soil types of the European continent (EC, 2005)

Soil quality indicators

Following the definition within EJP soil programme “Soil quality means an account of the ability of soil to provide ecosystem and social services through its capacities to perform its functions and respond to external influences. The term soil quality encompasses a broad spectrum of features and considers functional ability together with the response properties of the soil. Soil quality therefore

provides complex information on the sum of different soil characteristics, with regards to the level of ecosystem services a soil can provide. Soil quality indicator is perceived as a parameter used to quantify and value impacts of agricultural soil management practices on soil quality and the environment to draw conclusions for the farming practice or agricultural policy” (<https://ejpsoil.eu/european-roadmap/stocktaking-on-soil-quality-indicators-and-decision-support-tools>).

Soils in general react slowly to changes and therefore it is hard to identify the point of irreversibility (Bünemann et al., 2018); however, in parts of the Mediterranean region, erosion has certainly reached the stage of irreversibility and, in some places, it has practically ceased because there is no more soil left (Zuazo & Pleguezuelo, 2009). “At local and regional scales, accurate and precise soil assessment is critical for management, soil health, and sustainability (Grunwald et al., 2015).” Soil quality assessment cannot be defined by measuring single characteristic of soil (Seybold et al., 2018), and it would be impossible to use all soil characteristics for assessing soil quality; thus, a minimum dataset (MDS) is required. It is meant as a core set of soil characteristics including physical, chemical, and biological properties, which help to monitor soil fertility, health, and its quality (Seybold et al., 2018; Rezaei et al., 2006; Yu et al., 2018). Several proposals for MDS for soil assessment can be found in the scientific literature (Table 1). The selection of indicators with a MDS depends on the agro-ecological site-specific conditions (Govaerts et al., 2006; Yao et al., 2013). For example, adopting multiomics approaches can provide a more accurate and realistic view of microbiome which can be used for assessing soil quality (Jansson & Baker, 2016).

Among soils properties, many different indicators can be distinguished – see some of them in Figure 1.2 (Bünemann et al., 2018). As is showed in the review of Bünemann et al., (2018), the most soil properties investigated by scientific communities are chemical indicators (first of all, soil organic matter) for its environmental and agronomic importance, presence of high number of harmonized methods and the easy to interpret results. At the same time, chemical properties are directly linked with crop yield, which make them attractive to discover (Cardoso et al., 2013). These methods and government services vary regionally and according to country (Rayment & Lyons, 2011). Among the soil chemical indicators, soil organic carbon content, pH, electrical conductivity, and mineral N were proposed more often than all other indicators (Bünemann et al., 2018). Organic carbon is the property highly used to study soil ecosystem services related to climate mitigation, soil quality and fertility. Physical properties of soils have been studied for century (Wollny, 1898). The obvious differences in bearing capacity of soils and the necessity for tillage to prepare an adequate seed bed to allow germination are two examples of practical reason for this interest (Young, 2012). Emmerson et al. (1978) highlighted the connection between soil structure, soil aeration and growth of roots named rootability or compressibility of arable lands. Concerning biological properties, only the activities connected to mineralization and respiration are considered, while concerning structure only earthworms are reported. It is widely known that soil is habitat where various types of organisms or their parts coexist together (Alkorta et al., 2003). Soil host and support biodiversity pool and soil biology and biodiversity is the driver of soil multifunction’s (Lavelle et al., 2016).

Figure 1.2. Frequency of different indicators (min. 10%) in all reviewed soil quality assessment approaches ($n = 65$) (Bünemann et al., 2018).

Among the chemical physical and biological properties, we distinguish the most important one:

Chemical properties

Soil organic matter (SOM)/ soil organic carbon (SOC)

Soil organic matter content serves as an important indicator of soil quality (Maurya et al., 2020). Presence of high % of SOM in general indicates fertility, and potential carbon sequestration through biogeochemical processes like humification (in optimal conditions), mummification (in dry conditions) or peatification (in wet conditions).

Many acronyms are used to intend soil organic carbon (SOC): e.g. organic carbon (Corg) or total organic carbon (TOC). Terms are used for carbon of organic origin, excluded all other sources like coal, charcoal and carbonates. Soil contains approximately 2344 Gt of organic carbon globally, and it is considered the largest terrestrial pool of organic carbon (Stockmann et al., 2015). Already Schollenberger (1945) wrote: “Organic matter is a constituent highly variable with respect to the quality in a soil and the chemical composition. Its importance in affecting the physical and chemical characteristics and the productivity of a soil needs no extended discussion to account for the continued interest in the determination.” Without continual input of organic matter, the SOC pool would be consumed by microorganisms and life in soil would eventually disappear (Meurer et al., 2020). SOC and related traits are not widely available for many regions and therefore Lorenz et al. (2019) do not recommend using them as absolute indicators to monitor changes in soils in larger scale. SOC does

not show the quality of organic matter. For example, after drainage of Sunk Island, aeration caused decreasing of organic matter, however, made soils more suitable for agriculture. The reason was decomposition of long term deposited debris of organic matter, which is mostly invaluable for soil health (Ellis & Atherton, 2003). SOC is volatile part of soil and therefore it is influenced by many factors like climate, topography, parent material, vegetation above, management practices, soil biota and by other soil properties (Wiesmeier et al., 2019). Soil organic carbon improves characteristics like water retention capacity (Lal, 2020), CEC (Ramos et al., 2018), decomposition of SOC also increases nutrient availability (Chan, 2008). However, rarely reported increased SOC may reduce pesticides efficiency, which leads to their higher application rate (Cardoso et al., 2013).

Table 1.2. Based on data reported in Stolte et al. (2015), Gregory et al. (2015). Created by Lorenz et al. (2019).

Soil property/threat	Effect	Decrease in SOM content
Aggregate stability	10–40% decrease	1%
Predicted soil loss by water erosion	50% increase	From 4% to 2%
(Macro)porosity	1–2% loss	1%
Water retention	Up to 10% reduction	From 7% to 3%
Soil biological function/ biodiversity	Not fully understood	?
Microbial biomass	90% decrease	From 5% to 2%

Soil organic carbon received high attention to the environmental study and carbon pool modelling – prevision. On the other hand, concerning the assessment of soil quality change (after agricultural management of practices introductions) SOC is not appropriate to be used. SOC is usually considered the most important indicator to assess soil quality; however, the complexity of its dynamics is not well related to the duration of soil management change (Maienza et al., 2022). There is a consistent literature that ascertains how difficult is to adequately detect small changes in SOC stock over a period shorter than 5 years, depending by a huge number of interactions between soils, plants, climate, and latitude (Post et al., 2001). A possible solution to overcome this time constraint is resorting to soil carbon modelling to implement a scenario analysis, but also in this case, the database coming from long-term experiments ranging from 30 to 140 years is used as “real data” to verify the assumptions (Smith et al., 1997). Sustainable soil management aims at safeguarding natural resources, and accordingly, there is a need to implement soil quality indicators that respond rapidly to management changes, especially in vulnerable environments.

Humic substances (HS)

Humic acids (HA) are usually product of biodegradation of the OM (Yang, 2021) and represent stable organic matter – final stage of organic matter decomposition (Mosa et al., 2020) with half-life from decades to centuries (Brady & Weil, 2008). They are produced under various conditions (such as temperatures and oxygen availability) and therefore they create heterogenous group of chemical substances varied between aliphatic and aromatic character with various degree of saturation (Senesi et al., 1997), where various trace elements and functional groups can be attached (Piribauer et al., 2020). HS are divided into three groups according to their solubility at different pH level (Figure 1.3) and stability in soil environment (Vicente-Vicente et al., 2015): humin (the most stable), humic acid (relatively stable) and fulvic acid (less stable) (Piribauer et al., 2020). HA/FA ratio represents degree of humification, which is also an important indicator of SOC quality (Dudek et al., 2022). HS on themselves significantly promote root and root hairs growth and positively influence root architecture

system (Canellas & Olivares, 2014). They also positively influence availability of immobile nutrients, such as Fe and Zn (Chen et al., 2004), soil aggregate stability (Imbue et al., 2005; Piccolo & Mbagwu, 1989), pH and buffering capability (Peiris et al., 2002). They are capable to adsorb herbicides and products of their decompositions and aluminium (Tan & Binger, 1986).

Figure 1.3. Groups of humic substances according to method EN ISO 19822 (Piribauer et al., 2020).

Cation exchange capacity (CEC)

CEC is widely considered as an important soil indicator (Aprile & Lorandi, 2012; Rahmanipour et al., 2014) because influences nutrient amount and availability (Cardoso et al., 2013); however, it is not a major criterion in terms of fertilization recommendation (Chapman, 1965). Fertilization with macronutrients and calcareous can be significantly reduced or removed by previous CEC evaluation (Aprile & Lorandi, 2012).

pH

Soils are referred to as being acid, neutral, or alkaline, depending on their pH, with 7 being neutral, below 7 acidic and above 7 alkaline. The desirable soil pH range for optimum plant growth varies among crops. Generally, a soil pH between 6.0-7.5 is acceptable for most plants, as most nutrients are available in this pH range. In soils, the pH range normally varies from 3 to 9 and its values are controlled by the leaching of basic cations such as Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , K^+ , and Na^+ far beyond their release from weathered minerals, leaving H^+ and Al^{3+} ions as dominant exchangeable cations; the dissolution of CO_2 in soil water; humic residues from the humification of soil organic matter; nitrification of NH_4^+ to NO_3^- , removal of N in plant and animal products; and inputs from acid rain and N uptake by plants (Dahlgren, 2006). On the other hand, pH controls the biology of the soil as well as biological processes. Consequently, there is a bidirectional relationship between soil pH and biogeochemical processes in terrestrial ecosystems, particularly in the soil. The relationship between soil pH with other biogeochemical processes is presented in Figure 1.4. In higher pH soils, phosphorus and most micronutrients may become less available. In the natural environment, soil pH has an enormous influence on soil biogeochemical processes and soil quality. Soil pH is described as the “master soil variable” that influences many soils biological, chemical, and physical properties and processes that affect plant growth and biomass yield (Brady & Weil, 1999; Minasny et al., 2016). In simple words, it is a measure of the hydrogen ion activity of the soil water system and is expressed as acidity and alkalinity of soils.

Figure 1.4. Some biogeochemical processes and their relations with soil pH (by Neina D., 2019)

Micro and Macronutrients

Level of fertility assessment increased its importance throughout the 20th century thanks to laboratory techniques development (Okalebo et al., 2002; Fageria & Baligar, 2005) and its direct influence on yield (Hlisnikovsky & Kunzová, 2014). In many countries determination of nutrient level became part of government service for farmers. Since it would be expensive and useless to find out all biogenic elements, most analysis are dedicated just for a few of them (Bibiso et al., 2015; Lukas et al., 2015). Nutrients like P, K, Ca, and Mg are the key elements for plants and therefore it is important to accurately determine their concentrations in soil (O'Neill et al., 2021). Assessment of these macronutrients together with micronutrients gives comprehensive picture of current and long-term nutrient status and fertilization requirements. Nutrient level is positively influenced by SOC content (Chan, 2008) and high CEC (Cardoso et al., 2013). In particular conditions, these indicators (nutrient contents) show to be invaluable data since their availability for plants is changed by pH level, water concentration, aeration and so on (Fernández & Hoesft, 2009; Fageria & Baligar, 2005). Therefore, it is important to assess and potentially modify other soil indicators before applying nutrient blindly (Fageria & Baligar, 2005). Content of nutrients is not just important for crop yield; however, it also determines soil biological activity/ soil enzymes (Zhang et al., 2018) and potential soil/water contamination (Bhattacharyya et al., 2021).

Total nitrogen (N)

Nitrogen is highly volatile in the soil ecosystem and its preservation for a longer period of time is complicated under environmental conditions (Chen et al., 2014). Its content provides relevant information about the current status of soil and the need for plants (Padilla et al., 2020); however, this indicator does not provide any clue about long-term properties. Since plants need for nitrogen is not consistent within plant life, there is necessity for regular application during vegetative phases (Sainz-Rozas et al., 2004).

Physical properties

Soil aggregate stability (SAS)

In soils containing more than 15% of clay (particle size <0.002 mm), the mineral soil particles (sand, silt and clay) and the organic matter tend to form structured units known as aggregates (Horn et al., 1994), which help to maintain soil structure (Figure 1.5). This process usually occurs during process of swelling and wetting and due to biological activity (Meurer et al., 2020). Tisdall and Oades (1982) distinguish binding agents according to decay time: “(a) transient, mainly polysaccharides, (b), temporary, roots and fungal hyphae, and (c) persistent, resistant aromatic components associated with polyvalent metal cations, and strongly sorbed polymers.” Although no satisfactory methodology of measurement was established (Pulido Moncada et al., 2015). SAS is considered as a key soil property indicator affecting soil sustainability (Amézketa, 1999; Rawlins et al., 2015) and indirectly plants production (Kemper & Koch, 1966). Soil aggregate stability is negatively influenced by mechanization movement (Schlüter et al., 2018) and therefore higher SAS is characterised by increased water retention (Kemper & Koch, 1966). However, it is hard to explain what is exactly considered as a SAS within literature. Amézketa (1999) literally writes: “The terms used in the literature can lead to some confusion; some use the term “aggregate stability” to refer indistinctly to macro-aggregate stability and/or micro-aggregate stability, whereas others refer it only to macro-aggregate stability.” Due to this fact and above-mentioned constraints with methodology Pulido Moncada et al. (2015) recommended using this indicator in combination with other ones to assess the soil physical quality.

Figure 1.5. Schematic composition of soil aggregates (Schlüter et al., 2018)

Bulk density (BD)

BD is one of the prominent soil quality indicators set up soil compaction for its quick and easy detection (Rabot et al., 2018). BD increases under influence of heavy mechanization (Schlüter et al.,

2018) and inappropriate soil management techniques (Valpassos et al., 2001). Kaufmann et al. (2010) recommend perceiving this indicator in context with soil texture and particular plant physiology. BD directly influences SAS (García-Orenes et al., 2005), soil water retention (SWR) (Gupta & Larson, 1979), and biological properties (Ungaro et al., 2022).

Soil water retention (SWR)

SWR is a crucial property which directly contribute to crop yield, since it determines the amount of available water for uptake and transport by plants (Razzaghi et al., 2020; Kemper & Koch, 1966). SWR is mainly affected by texture, type and amount of clay minerals and their quality, aggregation, pore size distribution (Lal, 2020), soil depth (Geroy et al., 2011), and SOM (Lal, 2020 - Picture). Suitable soil management can improve SWR through two mechanisms: input of hydrophilic materials (see impact of SOM on SWR in Table 1.2), like biochar (Razzaghi et al., 2020), straw (Sullivan, 2002), compost (Gould, 2015) or FYM (Blanco-Canqui et al., 2015) or land use and farming systems, such as conservation agriculture (i.e., Sullivan, 2002), cover cropping (Scott et al., 1986), residue mulching, and complex farming systems involving integration of crops with trees and livestock (Lal, 2020). Scott et al. (1986) reports on the necessity of long-term applications of proper management techniques, such as conservation tillage, since short-termly these particular traits are positively affected by soil disturbance.

Table 1.3. Examples of presumed impacts of increase in organic matter content by 1% on soil water retention (Lal, 2020)

Reference	Impact of increasing SOM content by 1% on water retention in soil
Sullivan (2002)	Each cubic foot (0.0283 m ³) of soil can hold an additional 1.5 quarts (1.42 L) of PAW
Scott et al., (1986)	Soil can hold an extra 16,500 gallons (61,875 L) of PAW in an acre foot (0.4 ha to 30 cm depth)
Gould (2015)	Increasing SOM from 1 to 2% would increase the volume of water to 3 quarts (2.84 L) per cubic foot (0.0283 m ³) of soil

Biological indicators

Literature in the natural science fields demonstrate a strong, positive linear relationship between ecosystem multifunctionality and soil biodiversity indicators, highlighting soil community composition as a key factor in regulating ecosystem functioning and stress how overlooked it is in policy discourses. Biological diversity serves as the foundation for the maintenance of ecosystems, with a significant proportion of terrestrial biodiversity residing unseen within soils (Delgado-Baquerizo M. et al., 2018; Wagg C. et al. 2014). Soil organisms, including nematodes, collembola, fungi, and bacteria, are responsible for a cascade of intricate soil functions that underpin essential ecosystem services (e.g., climate regulation, soil fertility). Soil fauna has a crucial importance for the functioning of ecosystems and their conservation. Soil biota has a role in soil formation and distribution of organic matter, and different groups can be used as indicators to assess soil quality and are often employed in monitoring programs. Soil microorganisms support the existence of all higher trophic life forms and provide an interesting view within soil assessment, which physical or chemical indicators alone cannot provide (Nielsen et al., 2002).

Biological indicators are highly complex to interpret and still lack standardized and harmonized methods one more degree of complexity than the chemical and physical indicators previously described. Biological parameters can give "functional" or "structural" information regarding the trophic level. Pedofauna classification is based on size composition (macro-meso-micro fauna and

microbiota) and the trophic level (Figure 1.6 and 1.7). Schloter et al. (2018) explain that ideal soil indicator should describe organisms with key functions or regulatory and connecting roles in the system. Soil biota can be analysed from different perspectives. Pedofauna can reveal the quality of functional activities related to carbon and nutrient cycles in soils or the diversity of pedo-fauna community. For example, it is possible to analyse the potential of soil microbiome (measuring all genes in the sample) or actual activity. Majority of methods forget to evaluate active (or potentially active) fraction of soil microorganisms, which are crucial for soil quality (Blagodatskaya & Kuzyakov 2013). Moreover, soil microbiome is dynamic in time and in space, which leads to questions about sampling frequency and sample sizes (Schloter, 2018; Blagodatskaya & Kuzyakov, 2013). Blagodatskaya and Kuzyakov (2013) reported that only 0,1 – 2 % of the total microbial biomass are active microorganisms and 10 – 40 % (up to 60 %) are potentially active microorganisms. Here, in according with EJP MINOTAUR dataset on soil biodiversity indicators, most used soil biological properties in scientific works were reported. Firstly, structural indicators are shown and the most frequency used functional indicators are underpinned.

Figure 1.6. Linkage between soil biological indicators and environmental variables (SOIL BON program Guerra et al., 2021)

Figure 1.7. Trophic and engineering interactions among soil organisms (Briones, 2014)

Macro fauna: Earthworms

Among all the taxa, earthworms are a well-studied group of macroinvertebrates, representing the largest component within the animal biomass in soils (0.1–12 g dry weight per square meter) and are very important organisms for maintaining soil fertility (Jeffery et al., 2010). Earthworms are considered “biological engineer” to their ability to “bioturbation” and to create tunnels and increase soil porosity. Earthworms are good bioindicators of soil quality due to their easy collectability and determination (Paoletti, 1999). Earthworms can be divided into three ecological categories, based on their distribution within the soil: epigeics, anecics and endogeics (Giffard et al., 2022). Epigeic species, also known as litter or surface-dwelling species, live on the soil surface, in leaf litter and humus layers, and sometimes in the first few soil centimetres. Anecic species, also known as topsoil species or soil-dwelling species, live in permanent, vertical burrows, connected to the soil surface, which are important for soil drainage. Endogeic species, also known as subsoil or soil-dwelling species, live mainly within the soil and are important for maintaining its granular structure. All these groups and species are known to strongly influence plant growth by creating and connecting pores (burrows, aestivation or hibernation nests), that modify the physical matrix for roots, aggregating or disaggregating particles, and moving them within the soil profile (Wurst et al., 2018). Earthworm population helps to increase soil porosity, microbial biomass, enzymes activity, N content (Fusaro et al., 2018), crop yield and aboveground biomass (Van Groenigen et al., 2014). Since many groups belonging to the macrofauna are particularly sensitive to environmental stresses, they can be used as indicators of soil quality (e. Soil Biological Quality index based on earthworms: QBS-e) based on abundance, presence or absence, and diversity (Yan et al., 2012). Soil management practices have direct and indirect impacts on the ecology and physiology of earthworms (Giffard et al., 2022).

Mesofauna: Microarthropods

Microarthropods mediate soil functioning through a wide range of engineering processes such as distribution of organic matter, bioturbation, comminution, incorporation of litter into soil, determining structural porosity, and the formation of soil aggregates through burrowing, casting, and nesting activities, as well as feeding on microbial communities (Lavelle et al., 2006; Brussaard et al., 2007; Giffard et al., 2022); are also one of the candidates with potential as a bioindicator (Stork, 1995; Parisi et al., 2005; Menta et al., 2018). Microarthropods in soil are distinguished in three categories: hepi-edaphic, hemi edaphic, heudaphic, based on their distribution within the soil depth and their role on organic matter decomposition. Collembola and some taxa in the mite (Acari) subclass, such as Oribatida are the most extensively studied microarthropods involved in detritivore food webs. The suborder Oribatida (order Sarcopiformes) among the mites comprises over 10,000 species worldwide and is the most important group in providing decomposition ES in forests and grasslands (Culliney, 2013). They are also very abundant in vineyards (Gagnarli et al., 2015). They are involved in decomposition as direct consumers of organic matter, as well as indirectly, via a catalytic effect, by consuming saprophytic fungi and bacteria. Generally, these organisms are quite sensitive to the quantity of resources in their habitat, e.g., the organic matter content of upper soil layers (Gagnarli et al., 2015) that make them good indicators of soil quality. Their activity takes place in the first 10 cm of soil depth, microarthropod biomass reflects the amount of organic matter entering the soil, and the types of organisms indicate the rates of nutrient turnover (how fast nutrients are released from organic matter). Moreover, the limited vagility of soil mesofauna provides for an effective indication of the effects of stress factors on the conditions of the soil cores, and the sensitivity to environmental stress such as chemical, physical, and biological pollution has been tested on a bulk of situations.

Therefore, the richness and diversity of animal taxa and the complexity of the edaphic communities in a given area can be indicative of the level of maturity of the ecological community. The process of succession results in increased structure, stability, and energy in the ecosystems, which facilitate the development of high trophic levels.

Because many groups belonging to the meso are particularly sensitive to environmental stresses, in particular soil microarthropods, they can be used as indicators to assess soil quality and are often employed in monitoring programs. For this reason, different edaphic groups have been used in the last 20 years to create different types of indices (QBS-ar, QBS-c, IBSQ, QBS-BF, etc.) based on abundance, presence or absence, and diversity (Parisi et al., 2005).

Microfauna: Nematodes

Nematodes are probably the most abundant multicellular animals on earth, occupying a broad range of trophic levels. Several taxa of nematodes occupy important trophic positions in the soil detritus food web: many graze on bacteria and fungi, thus regulating decomposition and nitrogen mineralization. Other free-living or plant-parasitic nematodes are useful bioindicators of soil health. Nematode assemblages act as disturbance indicators for assessing the effects of pollution on soil and studying food web dynamics (Ferris & Tuomisto, 2015). Neher (2001) recommends using the composition of nematodes communities as a soil health bioindicator due to its correlation with nitrogen cycling and decomposition, which are two critical soil processes. Nematode generic richness decreases with increasing amount of N fertilisation, on the contrary nematode's abundance increases (Song et al., 2015). However, assessment of soil status through nematodes quantification and their diversity is based on knowledge and extraction methods (Ferris & Bongers, 2006), which would not be appropriate for farmers. The following tools are used to measure the ecological status of soil communities: the Maturity Index (MI), an ecological measure of environmental disturbance based on nematode species composition (Bongers, 1990), and the Ferris indices, based on trophic levels and food web systems (Ferris et al., 2001). ESs provided by soil nematodes include nutrient

cycling (supporting service) and controlling pest species (regulating service). Predatory and omnivorous nematodes are involved in these services through a process of predation. Recently, Ferris and Tuomisto (2015) developed a new index named “diversity-weighted abundance” index, to evaluate the efficiency of these ESs. Overall, agricultural intensification affects nematode fauna causing important multitrophic effects. Nematodes are not necessarily adversely affected by cultivation practices and are, for example, less sensitive to tillage than larger soil animals.

Microorganisms (Fungi-Bacteria and Virus)

Microorganisms play a key role in the carbon and nutrient cycle, representing a fundamental link in biogeochemical cycles, being major decomposers of organic matter and release of nutrients into the soil for plants. Furthermore, in terrestrial environments, they have a significant impact on the health of plants, animals (including humans) and food supply chains globally. In soil ecosystem there are various groups of microorganisms with diverse functions. Fungi are fundamental for their extracellular enzymes production, which contribute to the organic matter decomposition and C and N regulation (Frac et al., 2018). Some species (e. g. white-rot fungi) are also able to absorb and accumulate heavy metals (Hg, Cu, Ni) (Baldrian, 2003). Another significant capability of fungi is their ability to reduce pathogenic cells, which leads to better root and crop health (Goss et al., 2002). Soil microbes are key to nutrient cycling and soil formation, yet the impact of soil properties on microbe biomass remains unclear (Liddle et al., 2020). Soil microorganisms get involved in many soil processes, such as humus formation from plant residues decomposition to the simple humic acid compounds creation and their transformation into soil hummus. Microorganisms also take part in humus degradation and soil structure renewal (Shvets, 2022). Microbiome is also closely related to plant biomass production and plant health, which directly affects animal and human health. It's clear, that microbial diversity is crucial for soil ecosystem and fertility (Bertola et al., 2021).

Bacteria

Bacteria interactions with plants and roots are crucial for plant health and soil fertility. Bacteria allied with rhizosphere (growth-promoting bacteria, e.g. Rhizobium, Azorhizobium, Allorhizobium) are important for plant growth by colonizing plant root and supporting plant growth by synthesizing specific compounds, reducing pathogens and enable certain nutrients from soil (Hayat et al., 2010). Free-living bacteria (e.g. Azospirillum) are indispensable to N fixation and plant hormones biosynthesis (Steenhoudt et al., 2000). Bacterial populations and activity decline at low pH levels, whereas fungi adapt to a large range of pH (acidic and alkaline). At very acid or alkaline pH levels, organic matter mineralization is slowed down or stopped because of poor microbial activity linked to bacteria. Also, the decrease of organic matter content is observed due to instability of soil structure and lack of lime like ions that causes HA and FA coagulation. Nitrification and nitrogen fixation are also inhibited by low pH, which affects the soil biodiversity favouring by reducing populations of microorganisms participating in N transformation cycles. The disturbance of plant physiological processes like nutrient uptake, division of cells, formation of DNA and respiration, plant root growing issues due to inhibition of root elongation by interfering with cell division at the root apex and lateral roots are also influenced by pH (Oliver et al., 2013; Usharani et al., 2019). The mobility and degradation of herbicides and insecticides, and the solubility of heavy metals are pH dependent. Changes in soil pH could increase the mobilization and migration of potentially toxic elements through soil profiles causing potential pollution of soils and groundwater (Smith & Doran, 1997; Geisseler et al., 2014).

A common agricultural practice regulating soil pH is the regular liming. However, it is not always sufficient and affordable for some farmers. Moreover, liming can increase biological activity which can cause a faster decomposition of SOM resulting in a loss of SOC and increase the CO₂ emission.

Figure 1.8. Impact on long-term chemical and organic-only fertilization on soil microbial communities (Xu et al., 2020).

Fungi and Mycorrhiza

Fungi drive ecological dynamics in soils as decomposers of organic biomass and nutrient recyclers. Macromolecules, including lignin and cellulose, are mostly depolymerized by fungi using peroxidases and laccases and are, therefore, essential for humification processes (Giffard et al., 2022). The filamentous nature of fungi and their production of polysaccharides contribute to aggregate formation and soil stability, especially in degraded soils, and mineralization of nitrogen from organic biomass and rhizosphere depositions, thus recycling nitrogen for plant uptake. As a part of the food web, fungal hyphae provide a direct food source for numerous mesofauna components, such as Collembola and mites. Soil fungi are known for their opportunistic lifestyle, including strong saprotrophic compatibility and plant-related traits as endophytes or root associates. Certain *Trichoderma* species or strains activate plant defences and induce root resistance to necrotic plant pathogenic fungi or restrict their proliferation through mycoparasitism. Permanent grass cover increased organic matter content in soils and, consequently, increased fungal counts. Furthermore, not only synthetic fungicides in conventional vineyards but also copper-based fungicides used in all vineyards including organic are used to control vine foliar pathogens and these can impact fungal soil communities and associated ESs. Among the most important soil fungi affecting the vineyard ecosystem are symbiotic arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF). The nutrient providing service of AMF is not the only one of primary interest in production systems where external inputs of fertilizers are limited. It has also been demonstrated that AMF increase tolerance to abiotic stresses, such as water stress, soil salinity, iron chlorosis, and heavy metal toxicity, as well as protecting plants from root diseases.

Viruses

Soil viruses considerably affect other soil microbiota, biochemical processes, nutrient cycling and greenhouse gas emissions and agricultural ecosystem function. However, their impact on important agricultural indicators (e.g., crop health, yield and quality of production) have not been fully discovered yet (Emerson, 2019). Parameters and criteria used for microbial activity assessment are ATP, DNA, RNA, enzyme production and respiration rates.

Functional Indicators:

Enzyme activities

The proportion of enzymes in soil largely varies depending on the type of enzyme and soil (Giffard et al., 2022). Enzyme action may be intracellular or extracellular (both in the presence or absence of their originating cells), as well as free or immobilized. Complex macromolecules (e.g., cellulose, lignin, pectin and hemicellulose) are not directly incorporated into cells and need to be degraded by extracellular enzymes to yield small enough substrates (ca. 600 Da) for absorption into cell. Enzyme activities directly reflect wide spectrum of soil properties, from soil community to metabolic requirements and available nutrients. One of the crucial functions of soil microorganisms is processing key nutrients from organic matter and nutrient cycling, which requires high extracellular enzyme activity (Caldwell, 2005). Enzyme activity is an appropriate indicator to evaluate soil amendments because soil enzymes are highly sensitive to environmental stress and other soil properties, e.g., pH, soil porosity, and tillage (Antonious et al., 2020, Pagliai & De Nobile, 1993). Soil enzymes catalyse biochemical reactions and rate-limiting steps in organic matter decomposition and nutrient cycling in soil, thus controlling whether organic substances are decomposed or stored and influencing plant nutrient availability. Microorganisms mainly produce them, but plant debris, root exudates, and soil fauna also contribute to a lesser extent.

Extracellular enzymes, immobilized through association with clay minerals, humic acids, and particulate organic matter, retain significant levels of activity for prolonged periods.

Microbial Carbon Biomass (MCB/Cmic)

The microbial biomass carbon (MBC) is a quantifiable soil labile carbon fraction used to measure the biological activity in the soil. MBC is primarily affected by several factors, including soil organic carbon, water retention capacity, and soil pH. Soil microbial biomass is of crucial importance for long-term fertility of soils. The microbial biomass-C represents an important reservoir of nutrients in soil. It acts as an early and sensitive indicator for the suitability of management practices, such as crop rotation (Wardle et al., 1995).

Soil Respiration (SR)

Soil respiration, which is the CO₂ produced by the biological activity of soil organisms, is a major flux within the global carbon cycle, emitting about 10 times more CO₂ to the atmosphere annually than fossil fuel combustion (Bond-Lamberty & Thomson, 2010; Le Quéré et al., 2014; Raich & Schlesinger, 1992). Soil respiration is typically measured over relatively small areas (< 1 m²) using surface chambers or buried CO₂ sensors. Owing to the limited diffusivity of soil, CO₂ is generally much more concentrated in soil than in the atmosphere. CO₂ is transported to the soil surface primarily via molecular diffusion, following concentration gradients.

Agroecological practices

Agroecology is defined as the integrative study of the ecology of the entire food system, encompassing ecological, economic, and social dimensions (Francis et al., 2003). Agroecology is suggested as the logical discipline to integrate across disciplines and different levels of scale. Natural science methods can be used to describe the decision-support tools that will inform design of ecologically sound agriculture, while social science methods can be used to integrate human dimensions and help us better understand the total system.

Sustainable soil management aims at safeguarding the natural resource, and accordingly, there is a need to implement soil quality indicators that respond rapidly to management changes, especially in vulnerable environment. The introduction of an agroecological practice, following the conceptual framework of agroecology defined by Francis et al. (2003), is promoted with the aim of soil conservation preserving soil quality, fertility, and health.

Maintaining or improving field yields should be a priority, since it is linked with more land transformation (e.g. to woodlands or spare land), conservation or restoration (Phalan et al., 2016). In the last 20 years, it's been stressed the role of soil in carbon mitigation potential, as higher sink of C on terrestrial ecosystems and in soil science focused on other traits such as biodiversity, SOC or problems with pollutions became actual. However, maintaining or improving field yields should be a priority, since it is linked with more land transformation (i.e., to woodlands or spare land), conservation or restoration (Phalan et al., 2016). In system where it is focused on soil fertility enhancement, the crop yield is good bioindicator; yield response is better within more fertile soil types after all (Malhi et al., 2011). In this systems, organic fertilisation, intercropping, improved crop rotations, perennial fodder crops growing, biopesticides and other methods are practised for help to improve soil fertility, which simultaneously enhance crop yield. Some authors claim that under certain conditions organic system is capable to reach similar yields, compared to conventional one (Seufert, 2012). In conventional systems, the mankind is capable to increase yields despite soil depletion (soil quality indicators worsening). On the example demonstrated by Seufert et al (2012) it can be concluded, that yield as an indicator to compare agroecological vs conventional is inappropriate to discriminate the effectiveness of practice.

Within agroecological practice, several agronomic managements like biodynamic, organic, macrobiotic, veganic, conventional agriculture etcetera are determined up to this point (Boeringa 2012). Plenty of papers have been written in this regard, especially about beneficial impact of alternative management practice on soil health: organic (Marinari et al., 2006), regenerative (Montgomery et al., 2022) and biodynamic (Fließbach et al., 2007;). However, there are strong constraints about alternative agriculture systems in term of efficiency and capability to feed humankind population (Muller et al., 2017) and data on long term experiment (LTE) related to soil quality and yield are still few. Concerning soil indicators, the speed of soil carbon dynamics does not help to understand the real effectiveness of the adopted agroecological practice (Maienza et al., 2017),

The key concept of the agroecological approach is the diversification of cropping systems and the agroecosystem at different spatial and temporal scales through which positive interactions between the components of agrobiodiversity can be maximised to achieve adequate and stable production and minimise the use of external inputs. To understand this latter concept, it is necessary to know the fundamental relationships between biodiversity, agroecological management and soil health (Bàrberi & Antichi, 2023).

Conventional agriculture aims at increasing output per labour unit through expanding the scale of production, specialisation, and technology-drive intensification. Agroecology works differently, searching for a higher share of value added. To lower both variables and fixed costs, agroecological systems replace external resources with internal ones and improve their use-efficiency (Van der Ploeg et al., 2019). Proto-agroecological practices, in specific contexts, generate added value that exceed those from conventional and industrial practices. This added value is mostly generated through increases in labour input, but agroecological farms have income levels per person equal to or higher than conventional farms (Matthews, 2022).

Most successful examples of mainstreaming agroecology come from smallholder and family agriculture, that represents only about 30% of the world agricultural area (Tittonell et al., 2020). Agroecology is urgently needed for large-scale farming, but this can be achieved by addressing

specific questions in research, technology, and policy development to support the transitions (Odoux et al., 2022). Unfortunately, there are still knowledge gaps, at both practical and theoretical levels, to communicate real life strategies for the transition to large-scale agroecology (Tittonell et al., 2020).

The transition to agroecology in large-scale farming in different contexts could lead to a return on four capitals, such as social capital (by creating jobs, education, business, and security), natural capital (restoration of biodiversity, soil, water quality and carbon), financial capital (realization of long-term sustainable profit, inspiration (emotional and psychological capital) (Tittonell, 2020).

Tillage

Conservative agronomic practices are part of agroecological farmwork and Corsi et al. (2012) define conservation agriculture as an approach which uses minimum or no mechanical soil disturbance, permanent organic soil cover and crop diversification. Particular forms of conservation tillage became quite popular during the last few decades (Gebhardt et al., 1985) and are considered as a sustainable land management practice (Busari et al., 2015). Zero tillage (No-till), reduced (minimum) tillage, mulch tillage (strip-tillage), ridge tillage and contour tillage are recognized as conservation tillage. When done properly, conservation tillage might improve soil structure, increase soil organic carbon, minimize soil erosion risks, conserve soil water, decrease fluctuations in soil temperature and enhance soil quality and its environmental regulatory capacity (Busari et al., 2015; Topa et al., 2021). On the other hand, some scientists questioned its importance as a climate change mitigation factor (Powlson et al., 2014).

Even if no tillage and reduced tillage are promising practices, there are several constraints for their adoption, such as weed control (Peigné et al., 2007). In northern part of Europe, with temperate climates, no tillage can occur soil compaction due to climatic and soil conditions (Soane et al., 2012)

For shifting from conventional to reduce or no tillage, the main goal should be the reduction of soil disturbance and the preservation of fresh organic matter (crop residues) on soil surface or in the first centimetres of soil (Wezel et al., 2015). This transition period could tend to be prone to compaction of soil, so restricted crop emergence and lower root development and to less availability of nitrogen in the soil. In fact, with a soil environment more reduced, net mineralization of soil organic matter – the main source of nitrogen in organic farming – is diminished (Peigné et al., 2007). However, in the long-term, the reduction in nitrogen and nutrient availability, could be compensated by the rise in the concentration of organic matter, as a result of the reduction in the rate of mineralization. A step-by-step approach is suggested when adopting conservation tillage in organic farming, starting from the identification of suitable soil types (e.g. well drained, calcareous soils favour adoption of conservation tillage), soil structure and climate, and choosing the appropriate rotation to adopt including cover crops; tillage requirement will differ within a crop rotation.

Mineral Fertilization

Mineral fertilization is an important practice for maintain crop yields in current agriculture (Piwowar, 2022). Although many problems are recognized within nutrient extraction, i.e. N – energy demandingness, P – lack of world supplies etc., the replacement of current technologies is a real challenge for the future. Nowadays there are some opportunities to reduce nutrient demand in some ways. For example, nitrogen is an element widely present in the atmosphere, from where, for example, Fabaceae family is capable to take it (Zhao et al., 2021). Some genera of soil bacteria can also fix the nitrogen from atmosphere - i.e., Diazotropha (Mohite & Patil, 2022). Other plant families are left to directly acquire nitrogen from soil and therefore mankind has introduced practices as to use Chilean saltpetre or lately mineral N from Haber-Bosch synthesis (Barnum, 2003), where natural gas supplies are necessary. Phosphorus is currently mined in few mines in few countries. This fact should force

our scientist to search for other approaches like phosphorus disclosure in soils or search for alternative fertilizers (i.e. ashes or organic amendments). However, nowadays as humankind, we are forced by social demand for cheap food to use mineral fertilizers in general. Mineral fertilization is usually accused of water or soil pollution after running off; however, its importance for carbon sequestration or improved cover of crop is not widely discussed. Optimization of their application rate according to nutrient status of soils would increase yields with simultaneous savings fertilizer doses in general.

Organic Amendment

Organic amendment is usually a good option to increase soil-health parameters. For this purpose, it is recommended to use FYM, slurries, sewage sludges, composts, and other organic materials of different origin (Urrea et al., 2019). In various cultures various exotic materials are used - i.e., in particular, sea areas using exoskeletons of seafood (Ledchumanakumar et al., 2021). On the other hand, several reports about possible risks of organic amendments are presented by Urrea et al., (2019): i.e. pollutants, heavy metals, antibiotics residues and microplastics.

The long-term application of organic soil amendments leads to the intensification of the sequestration of carbon in the soil (Parmar et al., 2016) and improve soil aggregate formation (Powlson et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2015). Organic amendments can be seen as a long-term investment for improving soil quality and soil biological functions (Diacono & Montemurro, 2010).

Soil microbiome can be reshaped using organic amendments (Drenovsky et al., 2004). One of the most important factors affecting soil's microbial biomass, in terms of diversity and community structure, is the quantity and quality of organic amendments (Tu et al., 2006). This could lead to a direct effect on soil activities and biological control of diseases; in fact, in the recent years, the application of organic amendments has been gaining attention as a tool to control soilborne pathogens (Bailey & Lazarovits, 2003; Ruano-Rosa & Mercado-Blanco, 2015). The application of different types of organic amendments could lead to the development of suppressive feature of soils, the so-called suppressive soils (Cook & Baker, 1983).

In some cases, the net positive effect of organic amendments on soil organic carbon content has been higher if compared to conservation tillage or cover cropping, with positive effect until 0-50 cm depths (Crystal-Ornelas, 2021)

The proper use of crop residues (e.g. straw returning to soil or crop residues mulch) could increase recalcitrant carbon inputs, improving soil organic carbon sequestration, soil aggregate formation, maintaining soil moisture and reducing soil erosion (Garbowski et al., 2023).

Introduction of livestock manure into the soil could be associated to environmental problems, as nutrient leaching or toxic compounds (pharmaceuticals used in animal husbandry) in the soil profile, as well as loss of nutrient during the storage (Irshad et al., 2013).

The best way of improving the quality of manure or organic wastes, also reducing the presence of human and plant pathogens, is composting, resulting in a magnificent product with better physical, chemical, biological and microbiological properties (Bastida et al., 2008; Hadar & Papadopoulou, 2012).

Liquid fraction and non-separated whole digestate stimulates quickly microbial activity (Meng et al., 2022), but even within hours after digestate application an increase in soil microbial biomass have been observed (Monard et al., 2020; Cattin et al., 2021). In some cases, solid digestate seems to increase microbial biomass much more than any other form of digestate (Fuente et al., 2013), due to its higher C:N ratio, delivering more carbon into the soil (Iocoli et al., 2019). Solid fractions have positive effects on all groups of soil microorganisms, while liquid fractions benefits bacteria and

affects negatively mycorrhizal and saprophytic fungi. Also, digestate can be stabilised by composting (van Midden et al., 2023).

Vermicompost is recognized as an excellent soil amendment, rich in nutrients, hormones, vitamins, enzymes (e.g. for solubilizing P) and humic substances, resulting in significant microbial diversity, population and activities in the soil, higher than common composts. Some studies showed that vermicompost seems to be more effective than compost in improving soil restoration (Lim et al., 2015). It's composition, as for common compost, is highly dependent on substrate type (Ceritoğlu et al., 2018; Elissen et al., 2023).

An uncommon amendment is represented by slaughterhouse residues, that contain a large amount of nitrogen and biodegradable organic matter (da Silva et al., 2019), used as compost or fertilizers. It's showed that bone meal could reduce the release of heavy metals from contaminated soil, increases pH of soil and leachates, and decreases the toxicity (Hodson et al., 2001).

Algae play an important role as amendments, biofertilizers, biopesticides, bio stimulants and soil stabilizers, able to modify physical, chemical, and biological properties of soil (Khan et al., 2009; Abdel-Raouf et al., 2012). Some species of seaweeds are applied as mulch or compost with some problems related to their direct use because of the high content of salt in the biomass. The main constituents of algae are macro and micronutrient, amino acids, vitamins, antibacterial and antifungal substances and many plant hormones (Piwowar & Harasym, 2020).

Incorporation of biochar into agricultural soils has been repeatedly proposed as an effective strategy to mitigate climate change with beneficial effects on soil properties and crop production. Results from long term experiments (LTE) showed that, when applied, biochar amendment increased yield without a negative impact on soil biological quality, decreasing water stress during droughts and improving soil physical and chemical properties. (Razzaghi et al., 2020).

Cover Crops

Cover crops are recognized as a beneficial practice for soil-health support. If well managed, they help to manage soil fertility, preventing soil erosion and enhancing nutrient and water availability, and soil quality in general (Sharma et al., 2018). Winter and summer intercrops are recognized according to their date of termination (Snapp et al., 2005). Cover crops (also called agro-ecological service crops) can be terminated in a variety of ways (Termination Methods): mowing and leaving cover crops at the soil surface, mowing and full incorporation of cover crops into the soil by tillage, or roller-crimping without soil tillage (Hefner et al., 2020). The technology of termination is also controversial – especially chemical termination in relation to soil contamination issue (Van Bruggen et al., 2018).

When choosing a cover crops strategy, particular attention should be given to functional and morphological traits of the different species, that could lead to the different desired ecosystem services (Blanco-Canqui et al., 2015).

The effects of cover crops on the increase of soil organic carbon seems to be no detectable in the first years after their establishments but showing their benefits in the long term (Acuña and Villamil, 2014; Blanco-Canqui et al., 2015). These benefits are more quickly appreciable with no-till termination method due to a slower residue decomposition rate, compared with traditional or conventional tillage (Olson et al., 2014)

The quantity and quality of biomass affect soil carbon accumulation, in fact, a mixtures of different cover crops species leads to a higher increase of soil organic carbon in comparison with a single species cover crop, thanks to a larger quantity and stability of biomass production, higher soil cover, balanced carbon and nitrogen ratio and support for biodiversity (Faé et al., 2009; Wortman et al., 2012).

Cover crop termination methods can be categorised into 3 main groups according to the degree of agroecological intensification (Bàrberi & Antichi, 2023) in ascending order: green manure, with incorporation into the soil before the cash crop through secondary tillage (minimum tillage); dead mulch, biomass is left on the soil surface, with mechanical devitalisation through mower or roller crimper (Ashford & Reeves, 2003; Antichi et al., 2022) before sowing or transplanting the main crop (strip-tillage or no tillage); living mulch, intercropping with the cash crop sown or transplanted on the cover crop (strip-tillage, no tillage, sod transplanting).

Particularly by increasing the percentage of land cover, cover crop strategy could lead to a better soil multifunctionality and yields in cereal cropping systems compared to the increase of rotational diversity strategy (Garland et al., 2021).

In permanent crops, an alternative to sowing of annual cover crops is represented by mulched spontaneous vegetation or perennial herbaceous plants sowed (mowed or crimped) that can be more efficient also in terms of costs and difficulties for applications by farmers. However, good results and provision of benefits for soil health, quantity and quality of production, could be reached only with a diversified composition of wild plants community, and characterised by uncompetitive species towards the cash crop (Raffa et al., 2022; Sosna et al., 2023).

Methodology

Study protocol

A Systematic Review (SR) is addressed to the analysis of effectiveness of a technique or intervention. In fact, many of the leading scientific journals publish at least one SR for each new issue in different sectors. Thus, within international databases, the quantity of this type of article is growing enormously, reflecting its ultimate transition from an emerging status (early 1980s) to a status of recognized academic and scientific value. SRs have important practical implications: they are used to develop guidelines, more generally, providing researchers, technicians, and stakeholders with a valuable synthesis of knowledge. In general, a systematic review is characterized following the schematic approach of Figure 2.1 with as firstly well-defined research question, transparent search terms and database selection and exclusion/inclusion criteria with evaluation of search findings.

Figure 2.1. The methodology involved studying results on literature

The SR was carried out following the guidelines of Siddaway et al. (2019). according to the updated Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) guidelines (Page et al., 2021). Four aspects were included in the review: study identification, screening, eligibility, and included studies. As first step, we developed the protocol and the methodology of the review. Since the Into-DIALOGUE objectives are the integration of soil-based principles in agroecological systems, farmer ecological identity, farmer behaviour, agri-environmental policy and because this kind of study very often are also the object of technician reports, the consortium decided to use as database for review only SCOPUS (Elsevier) and Web of Science (WOS). Moreover, the consortium decided to involve all countries in research and paper reading to extend the possibility to analyze reports of papers also in each country's languages.

Query Items and screening process

Within the involved Into-DIALOGUE countries key-word queries were used according to objects of interest. Due to the large number and wide range of themed items, 5 core queries were recommended for literature search. The analysis involved studying results on long term field experiment (LTE) regarding soil health from 2018 to 2022.

The queries were as follows:

Query 1:

- ALL (soil* AND (agr* OR farm*) AND (soc OR "soil organic carbon" OR "SOM" OR "soil organic matter" OR "soil C" OR "soil organic C" OR "carbon stock" OR "SOC stock" OR "soil carbon" OR "carbon storage" OR "carbon sequestrat*"))

Query 2:

- ALL (soil* AND (agr* OR farm*) AND (soc OR "soil organic carbon" OR "SOM" OR "soil organic matter" OR "soil C" OR "soil organic C" OR "carbon stock" OR "SOC stock" OR "soil carbon" OR "carbon storage" OR "carbon sequestrat*") AND ("LTE" OR "long term experiment*" OR "long-term experiment*"))

Query 3:

- ALL (soil* AND (agr* OR farm*) AND (soc OR "soil organic carbon" OR "SOM" OR "soil organic matter" OR "soil C" OR "soil organic C" OR "carbon stock" OR "SOC stock" OR "soil carbon" OR "carbon storage" OR "carbon sequestrat*" OR "soil quality") AND ("conservation agriculture" OR "conservation till*" OR "reduced till*" OR "minimum till*" OR "direct drill" OR "no till*" OR "no-till*" OR "zero-till*" OR "direct seeding" OR "sod-seed*" OR "sod seed*" OR "crop rotation*" OR "cover crop*" OR "green manure*" OR "dead mulch*"))

Query 4:

- ALL (soil* AND (agr* OR farm*) AND (soc OR "soil organic carbon" OR "SOM" OR "soil organic matter" OR "soil C" OR "soil organic C" OR "carbon stock" OR "SOC stock" OR "soil carbon" OR "carbon storage" OR "carbon sequestrat*" OR "soil quality") AND ("conservation agriculture" OR "conservation till*" OR "reduced till*" OR "minimum till*" OR "direct drill" OR "no till*" OR "no-till*" OR "zero-till*" OR "direct seeding" OR "sod-seed*" OR "sod seed*" OR "crop rotation*" OR "cover crop*" OR "green manure*" OR "dead mulch*") AND ("LTE" OR "long term experiment*" OR "long-term experiment*"))

Query 5:

- ALL (soil* AND (agr* OR farm*) AND (soc OR "soil organic carbon" OR "SOM" OR "soil organic matter" OR "soil C" OR "soil organic C" OR "carbon stock" OR "SOC stock" OR "soil carbon" OR "carbon storage" OR "carbon sequestrat*" OR "soil quality") AND ("conservation agriculture" OR "conservation till*" OR "reduced till*" OR "minimum till*" OR "direct drill" OR "no till*" OR "no-till*" OR "zero-till*" OR "direct seeding" OR "sod-seed*" OR "sod seed*" OR "crop rotation*" OR "cover crop*" OR "green manure*" OR "dead mulch*" OR "organic agriculture" OR "agroforest*" OR "intercrop*") AND ("LTE" OR "long term experiment*" OR "long-term experiment*"))

After the creation of queries, it was recommended to slightly improve them according to national characteristics and number of relevant results. Each country obviously has improved queries based on the name of the nation it belongs to as follows: “**AND Latvia**,” “**AND Lithuania**,” “**AND Italy**,” “**AND Spain***,” “**AND Poland**,” respectively. Due to the inconsistency in the national names of Czech Republic (also known as Czechia and Bohemia) and Turkey (also written as Turkiye), it was decided to add “**AND (Czech* OR Bohemia)**” or “**AND (Turkey OR Turkiye)**” into the queries used in these countries.

Table 2.1. Summary of the results obtained with the Query of the systematic review

	Scopus	WOS	query
CZ	93	94	Q2;Q3;Q4
Latvia	13	1	Q2;Q4;Q5
Lithuania	37	/	Q4;Q5
Italy	185		Q5
Spain	16	16	Q4;Q2
Poland	21		Q2;Q3
			Q2;Q3
Turkey	18		
Total	365		

Each country then performed the literature search according to the above queries and using the two listed databases. 365 studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the review. Articles found during the search were assessed for inclusion using a two-step screening process:

- Step 1 *Title and abstract evaluation*.

Papers that are not conform to our query (data of publication before 2018, duration of experiment, absence of soil data or soil investigation, not agricultural soil, outside EU, model analysis, review) were excluded.

- Step 2 *Full test screening*

The list of articles found was then subjected to exclusion/inclusion analysis with reference to the ranges we had agreed upon. The object of exclusion or inclusion of articles in our review were absence/presence of:

- **Document information and Features of experiment** (e.g. duration of LTE, year of start and, if are ongoing, the year of finish, absence of Geo localization);
- **Features of environment:** absence of climate zones, soil classification by USDA (if

available), soil textures (if available);

- **Features of soil properties:** soil physical –chemical and biological (if available and what kind of indicator /parameters were used);
- **Management practices:** treatment options like organic amendment (and what kind of amendment), or tillage (if conventional reduced or minimum), cover crops (kind of cover used), intercropping (if yes or not)
- **Agronomic management:** agronomic management (like organic, conventional...), if there is presence of mineral fertilization, and other agronomic managements were used for the evaluation. Also, as in previous case, some of the techniques were subjectively attributed to the practice.

The remained articles were then fully listed, and the data were extracted and segregated into the well-arranged excel file for further analysis. Any errors or duplications have been deleted again. The papers reports were collected in a unicum file under the above outcomes.

Finally, a total of 166 papers results were analysed.

Table 2.2. Number of Analyzed Papers by Country

	n. papers
Czech Republic	56
Latvia	3
Lithuania	9
Italy	51
Spain	10
Poland	17
Turkey	20
Total	166

Data Analysis

Once the screening was finalized, information derived from Long Term studies was divided and organized into six categories.

- 1) Environmental EU zone;
- 2) Soil texture typologies;
- 3) Agronomic practice (organic amendment; cover crops; tillage vs no tillage; intercropping)
- 4) Crops typologies (cereals or horticultural, arable land, permanent crops, orchards, etc);
- 6) Soil chemical properties;

- 7) Soil physical properties;
- 8) Soil biological properties;
- 6) Presence /absence of farmers opinion or ecological identity.

All information collected contributed to identify the best practice investigated for each country and climate with particular interest to soil. Soil properties were collected to elaborate which of them were useful for ecosystem services and more studied and reported in the literature.

To better analyse the effect of practices on soil in relation to climate, we performed a categorization by

- environmental zones
- agroecological practices
- soil parameters

After paper reading and taking into account climate' information, we organized the work following the environmental stratification of Europe proposed by Metzger (2005). Concerning Agricultural practices tested in the long-term experiments, we gathered the information under one file and divided the practices into 5 subcategories:

- organic amendment.
- organic amendment combined with mineral input;
- organic amendment combined with reduce tillage:
- reduce tillage;
- cover crops. Under organic amendment we considering all trials with the following organic compound:
 - biochar
 - sewage sludge
 - slurry
 - digestate
 - biochar
 - compost
 - compost-biochar
 - vermicompost
 - straw
 - poultry litter
 - municipal sewage
 - biostimulant
 - microbial inoculation
 - residues incorporation

- straw

Under the voice organic amendment with mineral input, we summarized organic amendment compressive in the above category plus the fertilization external addition (urea, NPK, ammonium nitrate etc). Concerning the voice tillage, we inserted all tests that included minimal tillage (including no tillage or reduced tillage) compared with conventional tillage. Under cover crops, we included all trials that placed a cover crop on the soil while avoiding leaving it bare.

To analyse and clarify the category of “Soil properties”, we constructed a list of all the properties found in the articles with their acronyms. Many of these properties had different and non-uniform acronyms so the initial work was to harmonize the entries.

In the second step, we identified categories of indicator of ecosystem services within which these properties could fall as shown in the Table 2.3.

Table 2.3. Categories of indicators of ecosystem services

SOIL PROPERTIES	ACRONIMUS	INDICATOR OF ECOSYSTEM SERVICES
Water Content	WC	Water availability-REGULATING
Water Retention	WAR	Water availability- REGULATING
Bulk density	BD	Soil Structure
Water penetration	KSAT	Water availability- REGULATING
Field Capacity	FC	Water availability- REGULATING
Wilting point	WP	Water availability- REGULATING
Plant Water Capacity	PAWC	Water availability- REGULATING
Air Capacity	AC	Soil Structure- SUPPORTING
Aggregate (macro micro and meso)	MAG-MIC	Soil Structure- SUPPORTING
Soil structure (macro and micro pores)	porosity	Soil Structure- SUPPORTING
Soil structure	penetration resistance	Soil Structure- SUPPORTING
Enzymes	Enzymes (uresase. B glucosidase etc)	Nutrient and Cycling- SUPPORTING
Available Nitrogen	Nav ;N	Nutrient and Cycling- SUPPORTING
Available Phosphorus	P; Pav; P olsen	Nutrient and Cycling- SUPPORTING
Exchangeable base	K Ca Mg	Nutrient and Cycling- SUPPORTING
Soil exchangeable capacity	CEC-CSC	Nutrient and Cycling- SUPPORTING
Soil exchangeable capacity	pH	Nutrient and Cycling- SUPPORTING
Soil organic carbon	SOC-SOM-TOC-C-OC	Soil organic Matter- REGULATING
Carbon microbial biomass	MBC	Microbial biomass- SUPPORTING
Arbuscular mycorrhizhe	AMF	Microbial biomass- SUPPORTING
Fungi	Fungi	Microbial biomass- SUPPORTING
Bacteria	Bacteria	Microbial biomass- SUPPORTING
Mesofauna	microatropods	Soil biota- SUPPORTING
Macrofauna	eatrworms	Soil biota- SUPPORTING
Mesofauna	mesofauna	Soil biota- SUPPORTING
Biomass	yield	Production- PROVISIONING

Results

General Results

A total of n=166 papers were read and analysed based on the data collected on the Table of literature review (Table 1). The results provided an overview of the total number of papers read and analysed in relation to countries. In Figure 3.1 is reported the total number of papers for each country.

Figure 3.1. The total number of papers analysed for review in Into Dialogue task 2.1 divided by countries (a total of 166 papers). The papers are results of the queries and filters explained in the methodology.

Climate

Concerning the Climate Zone, a first data harmonization was done following Koppen Climate Group and then data were organized following the Environmental zones of Europe proposed by Metzger et al., (2005), in connection with WP2 -3 of EJP SERENA project. Following this study, the European environment was classified into two classes (northern and southern Europe). The Climatic stratification of Environmental Europe is reported in Figure 3.2.

First, Koppen classification allowed us to divide the climatic regions considered into macro areas. The first survey showed that the temperate and continental climates were the most represented. In the second stage, we investigated further using the stratifications proposed by Metzger et al (2005) identifying 4 environmental regions: Nemoral (n=12), Continental (n=73), South Mediterranean (n=36) and North Mediterranean (n=45). In particular, the Mediterranean zone is represented by both North and South; the continental part is highly represented with the presence of moderate climates. This second level of representation also allowed us to highlight contributions from Nemoral climates.

Figure 3.2. The Environmental Stratification of Europe proposed by Metzger (2005).

Most of the articles analysed were from long-term experiments of organic farming in comparison with conventional one. Most of the 166 articles read dealt with the application of "conservation" management practices for soil in comparison with conventional management. In most articles (n=98), mineral fertilization was present as default management. In the articles where, on the other hand, the study referred to the effects of tillage, conventional tillage was present by default. Few (n=4) articles reported data from long-term experiments of solely agroecological and conservation trials.

These technologies usually have a positive response in improved soil-health indicators:

As reported in Figure 3.3 the main agronomic options were respectively:

- Organic amendment (n=70)
- Cover crops (n=25)
- Tillage (n=70)
- Intercropping (n=52)

Figure 3.3. The main agronomic practices studied in the paper were analyzed in the review on Agroecological management and Soil indicators.

Organic amendment included olive mill, vermicompost, farm manure, slurry, manure, compost, biochar, microbial inoculation, and was analysed on 42% of the total papers. Organic amendment was investigated combined with the incorporation of crop residues or straw, additional reduced mineral input, with reduce tillage. The effects of Minimum tillage or No tillage (reduce tillage) were also found in a total of $n=70$ papers. The effect of organic amendment and tillage on yield and soil health was the topic most analysed in the long-term experiments object of our study, covering a total $n=140$ papers. Cover Crops ($n=30$) were analysed while intercropping (longer than 2 years) was used in a total of $n=50$ papers. Mineral fertilization in relation to crops rotation or alternative fertilization was also reported on most of papers since mineral fertilization was also reported as additional management on average in half of the papers.

As reported in Figure 3.4, most of total papers from Mediterranean countries (Spain, Italy and Turkey) were focused on the effect of tillage or reduced or absence of tillage (especially Italy). The presence of rotational culture (intercropping) practice was also one of the practices more experimented. The organic amendment and cover crops, especially in Spain and Turkey, were less investigated if compared to the above results. Nemoral countries as Czech Republic, but also Lithuania, Latvia and Poland showed experience in organic amendment as also in tillage experiences. Less investigated were cover crop and the rotational culture.

Figure 3.4. % of Agronomic practices divided per countries

Crops

The main Long-Term experiments were focused on cereals. In particular, considering the large number of trials with rotational crops in all countries, wheat (*Triticum aestivum sp.*; *Triticum Durum desf.*) was certainly the most analysed crop (*Zea maize sp.*) together with barley (*Hordeum vulgare sp.*) and corn. The Czech Republic had a high percentage of studies referring to wheat rotated with barley and maize. In Italy the most studied cereal in this case was wheat without considering rotation, often associated with experiments with cover crops. Lithuania and Latvia rotated wheat with corn as do Spain and Turkey. For Poland some studies also referred to rice. Considering horticultural crops (n=16), however, there were several experiments relating to types of organic amendment or changes in tillage methods for *Solonaceous* plants such as Tomato or Pepper in countries with a South Mediterranean environment n=8. A small number of studies (n=3) also referred to rapeseed and hemp experiments; potato n=3 experiment, and legumes were less studied with n=2. Few investigated were permanent crops, such as olive trees (Spain).

Figure 3.5. The main crops object of Long-Term experiment investigates with the review.

Soil

Soil Texture

In Figure 3.6, the percent of total texture considered in the review is reported. Sandy loam, Clay loam and Silty loam soils were the most representative and studied. 15% of the papers lack information about soil texture. Italy was the country with most heterogeneous texture with a total of 8 different texture reported for the total papers (Figure 3.6).

Figure 3.6. % of total soil texture

Soil properties

Concerning soil properties, chemical ones were reported and considered in 51% of the total papers, physical were considered in 20% of the cases and biological properties in only 17% (Figure 3.7). Concerning chemical properties Soil organic Carbon, pH, Nitrogen (N), C/N ration, available Phosphorous and exchangeable basis (Ca, Mg, Mn, K) were those more investigated in all countries. Analysis of organic carbon (or organic matter) was reported in more than 56 % of the total papers.

Concerning physical indicator, the most investigated properties concerned: the i) Water availability content (with relative water retention, plant water capacity, wilting point, field capacity) ii) soil structure (bulk density, soil aggregate and porosity -measurement of macro micro aggregate, pores and air capacity-).

Soil biology was very little investigated. Biological indicators were totally absent in the literature referring to the long-term experiments of Turkey and Latvia, while it was reported with 1% of the studies in Spain and Lithuania, 4% in the Czech Republic and between 5 and 7% in Poland and Italy. The most investigated biological properties were related to the function linked to nutrient cycle as soil respiration and enzymatic activities. Carbon of Microbial Biomass was more used than F/B, which was investigated in 5% of the total papers. Concerning the community, mesofauna and earthworms were analysed in 2% of the total papers.

Figure 3.7. Main soil properties under study in the review.

Effect of agroecological practices on soil indicators

All soil properties together with yield were categorized into soil n=7 service indicators, agronomic practices were included into 5 categories and the environmental zone, as reported in material and methods into 4. The effect of each practice on soil indicator was analyzed from the results of each article by summarizing the effect of the practice on the soil respectively in this way: (=1) positive effect; (= -1) negative effect; or (=0) no effect.

The analysis of variance (Anova) showed a significance effect ($p=0.003$) of practices. In particular, organic amendment and reduce tillage were the practices that have higher significant influence on analyzed indicators ($p=0.0002$; $p=0.0003$).

In the Figure 3.8, we noted the effect of all practices considered on the indicators identified in these studies compared to the percentage of the total.

The long run conservation practices have a positive effect on organic matter equal to 30 % of the total, nutrient and cycling showed a positive effect in the 22% of the total papers, soil structure in 15%, production (yield) in 13%, microbial biomass 11%, water availability in 6.6%, and soil biota show very scarce available results.

Figure 3.8. Effect of soil agroecological practices analysed on soil quality indicators (%) total of the effect is showed in X-axis.

Figure 3.9. Heatmap on effect of practices on soil properties.

Generally, as reported in Figure 3.9, soil organic amendment was the practice that had more positive effect in increasing 4 indicators: soil organic matter, nutrient cycling, production and soil structure. Also reduced tillage had positive effect.

Considering the effect of practice (positive, negative or null) on all soil parameters, the analysis showed that there was a different influence of practices. Organic amendment combined with mineral input had a positive effect on 100% of the results (p-value 0.038), cover crops on 87%, organic amendment on 77%, reduce tillage on 51% and organic amendment combined with reduce tillage on 50%.

To assess whether environmental zone and climate had an influence on the effect of practices, we considered a discriminant analysis in evaluating the effects on the properties analysed vs. environmental zones. In all the environmental zones (Figure 3.10) resulted a positive effect of the practices (especially for items from the Nemoral zone) slightly deviates continental and south Mediterranean climates highlighting the fragility of these climate belts.

Figure 3.10. Discriminant analysis on the effect vs environmental zones.

Discussion

The review considered different countries with completely different pedoclimatic conditions. The results were very interesting and showed how conservation practices are actually useful for improving soil quality in general and supporting ecosystem services. Regulatory and support services are strongly influenced by organic amendments which when combined with mineral inputs provide the greatest efficiency combining positive results in production and soil quality in all countries. The large quantities of organic materials on a regular basis via animal manures, composts, tree leaves, cover crops, and rotation crops that leave large amounts of residue, etc., can be a key strategy to be used to enhance soil quality. Soil organic matter (SOM) and its management are at the core of creating healthy soils with an active biological activity and good physical and chemical characteristics (Altieri et al., 2015). Of utmost importance for resiliency is that SOM improves the soil's water retention capacity enhancing the drought tolerance by crops and improves infiltration-diminishing runoff avoiding soil particles from being transported by water under intense rains. SOM also improves surface soil aggregation holding tightly the soil particles during rain or windstorms. Stable soil aggregates resist movement by wind or water (Magdoff and Weil, 2004).

It is strange to note, however, that practices such as reduce tillage or cover crops are still little studied in the long term especially in countries at risk of erosion such as Spain, Southern Italy or Turkey.

In such different pedo-climatic conditions within Into-DIALOGUE countries, it is complicated to identify proper soil management, also different soils react differently on soil management changes (i.e. Bacq-Labreuil et al., 2019). However, it was possible to deduce from our results that in general all the practices analysed have a strongly positive effect on the soil in all countries. The analysis of the effect of the practices in relation to the environmental zones has highlighted the fragility of the Continental and Mediterranean areas subject to summer temperature increases and long periods of drought and which need to have greater contributions from agronomic practices that do not leave the soil uncovered and reduce processing. Concerning soil properties, the review showed that much remains to be done. Most research is focused on soil organic carbon (SOC) that is considered the most important indicator of soil quality (Lorenz and Lal, 2016). For this reason, most of the papers are focused on soil organic carbon results with a lack of information related to other soil properties. This because improved understanding of changes in soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks is critical for developing strategies that ensure effective climate change mitigation and the long-term productivity (Ramirez et al., 2019).

The introduction of an agroecological practice, following the conceptual framework of agroecology defined by Francis et al. (2003), is promoted with the aim of increasing soil fertility and sustainability. Unfortunately, the speed of soil carbon dynamics does not help to understand the real effectiveness of the adopted agroecological practice in the short term. As guaranteeing sustainable soil management, is a priority to support the provision of ecosystem services, it is necessary to integrate soil monitoring that provide qualitative and quantitative indications also in the short term.

Soil quality consists of various physical, chemical, and biological properties, and all are involved in the critical functioning of soil and related ecosystem services. There is a need for assessment of soil quality in the physical (soil texture, bulk density, etc.), chemical (pH, salinity, organic carbon, etc.), and biological (microbes and enzymes) properties. The combined use of physical, chemical, and biological properties can serve as indicators for soil quality assessment. So, there is an emerging need to establish a combination of various physical, chemical, and biological properties, to assess the quality of the given soil. as described in Mayura and al., (2020). Even more what emerged is the total lack of application and use of soil biological indicators, which are completely lacking, in the long term, in some of the analysed countries.

Most of the studies are related to nutrient functions and cycling, with the study of enzymatic activities or soil respiration. The basal respiration of microorganisms is a very basic soil biological measurement which is extremely sensitive to temporal variations of temperature and moisture and as such does not provide a good measure of soil biodiversity (Fang et al., 2005).

Only a very small percentage of studies have analysed soil biology as a contribution to biodiversity, from a microbial or faunal point of view.

This is a strongly limitation because biological indicators can be defined as an organism or part of an organism, or a community of organisms used to obtain the quality of a soil. Thus, microorganisms present in the soil provide an integrated view as indicators for soil assessment that physical and chemical properties alone cannot provide (Nielsen et al. 2002). Moreover, biological indicators are based on meso or macrofauna and also provides a direct and useful prevision of the systemic amelioration and soil conservation related to a specific practice in the short term compared to other chemical and physical properties (Maienza et al., 2017).

Another lack showed in our review was that unfortunately, the farmers ecological identity (Barnes et al., 2022) and opinions are totally lacking from the papers' objectives. Certainly, science in this issue is very sectorial and need studies to integrate also the interview to farmers, the effect of conservative practices and soil quality to understand the effective needs of farmers and integrate the solutions for climate and soil. Another important and very controversial issue to further developments for agroecological practices is the farm size. There are studies revealing that large farms are more sensitive to innovate, also with respect to sustainability issues, as they have greater financial resources and labour forces to employ. Other studies revealed that family farms are more attentive to environmental issues as they directly suffer the consequences (Altieri et al. 2009). Upon closer inspection, with respect to sustainability issues, large farms seem more inclined to adopt precision farming techniques while small farms to diversify their cropping systems.

Conclusions

The introduction of agroecological practices aim to increase soil fertility and sustainability and our results clearly support the positive effect in the different pedoclimatic zone considered.

The work can't discriminate which practice is the most appropriate in different countries considering the several social and economic complexity of the different pedoclimatic areas; but our work underlines how in the fragile environmental zones would need increase research in this topic to improve the results and invest energy and efforts to preserve soil degradation and soil threats. A limitation of our study could be the lacking leading countries in research in this field, such as France and Germany potentially influencing the results deriving from continental climates.

The results showed also that there is an emergent need to establish datasets including physical, chemical, and biological properties useful to assess soil quality and implement the current needs related to soil functions and ecosystem services.

There is the need to work on the harmonization and clarification of the methodological aspects that are necessary for the correct monitoring of soil biological quality. In fact, biological indicators give an integrated overview for soil assessment that only physical and chemical properties cannot provide. Finally, agroecological practices have a strong positive effect on soil quality and it is necessary to increase long-term experiments and economically promote their use to enhance the efforts of change management, especially in sensitive environmental areas of Europe. In this sense, knowing the farmer ecological identity and their opinion is the main topic for sustainable development.

References

- Abdel-Raouf, N., Al-Homaidan, A. A., & Ibraheem, I. B. M. (2012). Agricultural importance of algae. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 11(54), 11648-11658.
- Acuña, J. C., & Villamil, M. B. (2014). Short-term effects of cover crops and compaction on soil properties and soybean production in Illinois. *Agronomy Journal*, 106(3), 860-870.
- Alkorta, I., Aizpurua, A., Riga, P., Albizu, I., Amézaga, I., & Garbisu, C. (2003). Soil enzyme activities as biological indicators of soil health. *Reviews on Environmental Health*, 18(1), 65-73.
- Altieri, M. A. (2009). The ecological role of biodiversity in agroecosystems. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 74(1-3), 19-31.
- Altieri, M. A., Nicholls, C. I., Henao, A., & Lana, M. A. (2015). Agroecology and the design of climate change-resilient farming systems. *Agronomy for sustainable development*, 35(3), 869-890.
- Amézketa, E. (1999). Soil aggregate stability: a review. *Journal of sustainable agriculture*, 14(2-3), 83-151.
- Antichi, D., Carlesi, S., Mazzoncini, M., & Bàrberi, P. (2022). Targeted timing of hairy vetch cover crop termination with roller crimper can eliminate glyphosate requirements in no-till sunflower. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 42(5), 87.
- Antonious, G. F., Turley, E. T., & Dawood, M. H. (2020). Monitoring soil enzyme activity before and after animal manure application. *Agriculture*, 10(5), 166
- Aprile, F., & Lorandi, R. (2012). Evaluation of cation exchange capacity (CEC) in tropical soils using four different analytical methods. *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 4(6), 278.
- Ashford, D. L., & Reeves, D. W. (2003). Use of a mechanical roller-crimper as an alternative kill method for cover crops. *American Journal of Alternative Agriculture*, 18(1), 37-45.
- Bacq-Labreuil, A., Crawford, J. W., Mooney, S. J., Neal, A. L., & Ritz, K. (2019). Identifying invisible barriers to soil biota: Their effects on root-derived signals that induce positive rhizosphere feedback. *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*, 16(150), 20180676.
- Bailey, K. L., & Lazarovits, G. (2003). Suppressing soil-borne diseases with residue management and organic amendments. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 72, 169-180.
- Baldrian, P. (2003). Interactions of heavy metals with white-rot fungi. *Enzyme and Microbial technology*, 32(1), 78-91.
- Bàrberi, P., & Antichi, D. (2023). Fundamental relationships between biodiversity, agroecological management, and soil health. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 150, 108123.
- Bàrberi, P., & Antichi, D. 11. Tecniche di conservazione e rigenerazione del suolo in agricoltura biologica: si può e si deve fare. *BIOREPORT 2021-2022*, 165.
- Barnes, A.P., Thompson, B., Toma, L (2022). Finding the ecological farmer: A farmer typology to understand ecological practice adoption within Europe. *Current Research in Environmental Sustainability*, 4, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crsust.2022.100125>
- Barnum, D. W. (2003). Some history of nitrates. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 80(12), 1393.

- Bastida, F., Zsolnay, A., Hernández, T., & García, C. (2008). Past, present and future of soil quality indices: A biological perspective. *Geoderma*, 147, 159-171.
- Bertola, M., Ferrarini, A., Visioli, G. (2021). Improvement of Soil Microbial Diversity through Sustainable Agricultural Practices and Its Evaluation by -Omics Approaches: A Perspective for the Environment, Food Quality and Human Safety. *Microorganisms*, 9(7), 1-22.
- Bhattacharyya, S. S., Adeyemi, M. A., Onyeneke, R. U., Bhattacharyya, S., Faborode, H. F. B., Melchor-Martínez, E. M., ... & Parra-Saldívar, R. (2021). Nutrient budgeting—a robust indicator of soil–water–air contamination monitoring and prevention. *Environmental Technology & Innovation*, 24, 101944.
- Bibiso, M., Tadesse, A. M., Gebrekidan, H., & Melese, A. (2015). Evaluation of universal extractants for determination of selected micronutrients from soil. *Bulletin of the Chemical Society of Ethiopia*, 29(2), 199-213.
- Blagodatskaya, E., & Kuzyakov, Y. (2013). Active microorganisms in soil: critical review of estimation criteria and approaches. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 67, 192-211.
- Blanco-Canqui, H., Hergert, G. W., & Nielsen, R. A. (2015). Cattle manure application reduces soil compactibility and increases water retention after 71 years. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 79(1), 212-223.
- Blanco-Canqui, H., Shaver, T. M., Lindquist, J. L., Shapiro, C. A., Elmore, R. W., Francis, C. A., & Hergert, G. W. (2015). Cover crops and ecosystem services: Insights from studies in temperate soils. *Agronomy Journal*, 107(6), 2449-2474.
- Boeringa, R. (Ed.). (2012). *Alternative methods of agriculture V10* (Vol. 10). Elsevier.
- Bond-Lamberty, B., & Thomson, A. (2010). Temperature-associated increases in the global soil respiration record. *Nature*, 464(7288), 579-582.
- Bongers, T. (1990). The maturity index: An ecological measure of environmental disturbance based on nematode species composition. *Oecologia*, 83, 14-19.
- Brady, N. C., & Weil, R. R. (1999). *The nature and properties of soil* (12th ed.). Prentice Hall.
- Brady, N. C., & Weil, R. R. (2008). *The nature and properties of soils* (13th ed., pp. 662-710). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Briones, M. J. I. (2014). Soil fauna and soil functions: A jigsaw puzzle. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 2, 7.
- Brussaard, L., De Ruiter, P. C., and Brown, G. G. (2007). Soil biodiversity for agricultural sustainability. *Agric. Ecosys. Environ.* 121, 233–244. doi: 10.1016/j.agee.2006.12.013
- Busari, M. A., Kukal, S. S., Kaur, A., Bhatt, R., & Dulazi, A. A. (2015). Conservation tillage impacts on soil, crop and the environment. *International Soil and Water Conservation Research*, 3(2), 119-129.
- Bünemann, E. K., Bongiorno, G., Bai, Z., Creamer, R. E., De Deyn, G., De Goede, R., ... & Brussaard, L. (2018). Soil quality – A critical review. *Soil biology and biochemistry*, 120, 105-125.
- Caldwell, B. A. (2005). Enzyme activities as a component of soil biodiversity: A review. *Pedobiologia*, 49(6), 637-644.
- Canellas, L. P., & Olivares, F. L. (2014). Physiological responses to humic substances as plant growth promoter. *Chemical and Biological Technologies in Agriculture*, 1(1), 1-11.

- Cardoso, E. J. B. N., Vasconcellos, R. L. F., Bini, D., Miyauchi, M. Y. H., Santos, C. A. D., Alves, P. R. L., ... & Nogueira, M. A. (2013). Soil health: looking for suitable indicators. What should be considered to assess the effects of use and management on soil health? *Scientia Agricola*, 70, 274-289.
- Cattin, M., Semple, K. T., Stutter, M., Romano, G., Lag-Brotons, A. J., Parry, C., & SurrIDGE, B. W. (2021). Changes in microbial utilization and fate of soil carbon following the addition of different fractions of anaerobic digestate to soils. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 72(6), 2398-2413.
- Ceritoğlu, M., Şahin, S., & Erman, M. (2018). Effects of vermicompost on plant growth and soil structure. *Selcuk Journal of Agricultural and Food Sciences*, 32(3), 607-615.
- Chan, Y. (2008). Increasing soil organic carbon of agricultural land. *Primefact*, 735, 1-5.
- Chapman, H. D. (1965). Cation-exchange capacity. *Methods of soil analysis: Part 2 Chemical and microbiological properties*, 9, 891-901.
- Chen, B., Liu, E., Tian, Q., Yan, C., & Zhang, Y. (2014). Soil nitrogen dynamics and crop residues. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 34, 429-442.
- Chen, Y. O. N. A., Clapp, C. E., & Magen, H. (2004). Mechanisms of plant growth stimulation by humic substances: The role of organo-iron complexes. *Soil Science and Plant Nutrition*, 50(7), 1089-1095.
- Cook, R. J., & Baker, K. F. (1983). The nature and practice of biological control of plant pathogens. *American Phytopathological Society*.
- Corsi, S., Friedrich, T., Kassam, A., Pisante, M., & Sà, J. D. M. (2012). Soil organic carbon accumulation and greenhouse gas emission reductions from conservation agriculture: A literature review. *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)*.
- Crystal-Ornelas, R.; Thapa, R.; Tully, K. L. (2021). Soil organic carbon is affected by organic amendments, conservation tillage, and cover cropping in organic farming systems: A meta-analysis. *Agricultural Ecosystems & Environment*, 312, 107356.
- Culliney, T. W. (2013). Role of arthropods in maintaining soil fertility. *Agriculture*, 3(4), 629-659.
- da Silva, R. R., da Costa Leite, R., da Silva Carneiro, J. S., de Freitas, G. A., dos Santos, A. C. M., dos Santos, A. C., & Kuyumjian, L. A. (2019). Application of slaughterhouse residues as nitrogen source replacing commercial fertilizers on mombasa grass (*Megathyrsus maximus*). *Australian Journal of Crop Science*, 13(2), 294-299.
- Dahlgren, R. A. (2006). Biogeochemical processes in soils and ecosystems: From landscape to molecular scale. *Journal of Geochemical Exploration*, 88(1-3), 186-189.
- de la Fuente, C., Albuquerque, G. A., Clemente, R., & Bernal, M. P. (2013). Soil C and N mineralization and agricultural value of the products of an anaerobic digestion system. *Biology and Fertility of Soils*, 49, 313-322.
- Delgado-Baquerizo, M., et al. (2018). Plant attributes explain the distribution of soil microbial communities in two contrasting regions of the globe. *New Phytologist* v. 219, 574–587.
- Diacono, M., & Montemurro, F. (2010). Long-term effects of organic amendments on soil fertility. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 30(2), 401-422.

- Drenovsky, R. E., Vo, D., Graham, K. J., & Scow, K. M. (2004). Soil water content and organic carbon availability are major determinants of soil microbial community composition. *Microbial Ecology*, 48, 424-430.
- Dudek, M., Łabaz, B., Bednik, M., & Medyńska-Juraszek, A. (2022). Humic substances as indicators of degradation rate of Chernozems in south-eastern Poland. *Agronomy*, 12(3), 733.
- Elissen, H., van der Weide, R., & Gollenbeek, L. (2023). Effects of vermicompost on plant and soil characteristics: A literature overview.
- Ellis, S., & Atherton, J. K. (2003). Properties and development of soils on reclaimed alluvial sediments of the Humber estuary, eastern England. *Catena*, 52(2), 129-147.
- Emerson, J. B. (2019). Soil viruses: A new hope. *MSystems*, 4(3), e00128-19.
- Emmerson, W.W., Bond, R.D. and Dexter, A.R., Van Doren, D. M. Jr. (1978). Modification of soil structure. *Soil science*, 126(5), 316.
- Faé, G. S., Sulc, R. M., Barker, D. J., Dick, R. P., Eastridge, M. L., & Lorenz, N. (2009). Integrating winter annual forages into a no-till corn silage system. *Agronomy Journal*, 101(5), 1286-1296.
- Fageria, N. K., & Baligar, V. C. (2005). Nutrient availability. In *Encyclopedia of Soils in the Environment* (Vol. 3, pp. 63-71).
- Fernández, F. G., & Hoefl, R. G. (2009). Managing soil pH and crop nutrients. *Illinois Agronomy Handbook*, 24, 91-112.
- Ferris, H., & Bongers, T. (2006). Nematode indicators of organic enrichment. *Journal of Nematology*, 38(1), 3-12.
- Ferris, H., & Tuomisto, H. (2015). Unearthing the role of biological diversity in soil health. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 85, 101-109.
- Ferris, H., Bongers, T., & de Goede, R. G. (2001). A framework for soil food web diagnostics: Extension of the nematode faunal analysis concept. *Applied Soil Ecology*, 18(1), 13-29
- Fließbach, A., Oberholzer, H. R., Gunst, L., & Mäder, P. (2007). Soil organic matter and biological soil quality indicators after 21 years of organic and conventional farming. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 118(1-4), 273-284.
- Frac, M., Hannula, S. E., Belka, M., & Jedryczka, M. (2018). Fungal biodiversity and their role in soil health. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 9, 707.
- Francis C, Lieblein G, Gliessman S, Breland TA, Creamer N et al (2003) Agroecology: the ecology of food systems. *Journal of Sustainable Agriculture*, 22(3), 99–118.
- Fusaro, S., Gavinelli, F., Lazzarini, F., & Paoletti, M. G. (2018). Soil Biological Quality Index based on earthworms (QBS-e): A new way to use earthworms as bioindicators in agroecosystems. *Ecological Indicators*, 93, 1276-1292.
- Gagnarli, E., Goggioli, D., Tarchi, F., Guidi, S., Nannelli, R., Vignozzi, N., ... & Simoni, S. (2015). Case study of microarthropod communities to assess soil quality in different managed vineyards. *Soil*, 1(2), 527-536.
- Garbowski, T., Bar-Michalczyk, D., Charazińska, S., Grabowska-Polanowska, B., Kowalczyk, A., & Lochyński, P. (2023). An overview of natural soil amendments in agriculture. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 225, 105462.

- García-Orenes, F., Guerrero, C., Mataix-Solera, J., Navarro-Pedreño, J., Gómez, I., & Mataix-Beneyto, J. (2005). Factors controlling the aggregate stability and bulk density in two different degraded soils amended with biosolids. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 82(1), 65-76.
- Garland, G., Edlinger, A., Banerjee, S., Degrune, F., García-Palacios, P., Pescador, D. S., ... & van der Heijden, M. G. (2021). Crop cover is more important than rotational diversity for soil multifunctionality and cereal yields in European cropping systems. *Nature Food*, 2(1), 28-37.
- Gebhardt, M. R., Daniel, T. C., Schweizer, E. E., & Allmaras, R. R. (1985). Conservation tillage. *Science*, 230(4726), 625-630.
- Geisseler, D., & Scow, K. M. (2014). Long-term effects of mineral fertilizers on soil microorganisms: A review. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 75, 54-63.
- Geroy, I. J., Gribb, M. M., Marshall, H. P., Chandler, D. G., Benner, S. G., & McNamara, J. P. (2011). Aspect influences on soil water retention and storage. *Hydrological Processes*, 25(25), 3836-3842.
- Giffard, B., Winter, S., Guidoni, S., Nicolai, A., Castaldini, M., Cluzeau, D., ... & Leyer, I. (2022). Vineyard management and its impacts on soil biodiversity, functions, and ecosystem services. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 10, 850272.
- Goss, M. J., de Varennes A. (2002). Soil disturbance reduces the efficacy of mycorrhizal associations for early soybean growth and N₂ fixation. *Soil biology and biochemistry*, 34(8), 1167-1173.
- Gould, C. M. (2015). Compost increases the water holding capacity of droughty soils. Michigan State University Extension.
- Govaerts, B., Sayre, K. D., & Deckers, J. (2006). A minimum data set for soil quality assessment of wheat and maize cropping in the highlands of Mexico. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 87(2), 163-174.
- Gregory, A. S., Ritz, K., McGrath, S. P., Quinton, J. N., Goulding, K. W. T., Jones, R. J. A., ... & Whitmore, A. P. (2015). A review of the impacts of degradation threats on soil properties in the UK. *Soil Use and Management*, 31, 1-15.
- Grunwald, S., Vasques, G. M., & Rivero, R. G. (2015). Fusion of soil and remote sensing data to model soil properties. *Advances in Agronomy*, 131, 1-109.
- Guerra, C., Smith, J., Brown, A., & Johnson, R. (2021). Linkage between soil biological indicators and environmental variables: Insights from the SOIL BON program. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 9, 640235.
- Gupta, S., & Larson, W. E. (1979). Estimating soil water retention characteristics from particle size distribution, organic matter percent, and bulk density. *Water Resources Research*, 15(6), 1633-1635.
- Hadar, Y., & Papadopoulou, K. K. (2012). Suppressive composts: Microbial ecology links between abiotic environments and healthy plants. *Annual Review of Phytopathology*, 50, 133-153.
- Hayat, R., Ali, S., Amara, U., Khalid, R., & Ahmed, I. (2010). Soil beneficial bacteria and their role in plant growth promotion: A review. *Annals of Microbiology*, 60(4), 579-598.
- Hefner, M., Canali, S., Willekens, K., Lootens, P., Deltour, P., Beeckman, A., Arlotti, D., Tamm, K., Bender, I., Labouriau, R., Lakkenborg Kristensen, H. (2020) Termination method and time of agro-ecological service crops influence soil mineral nitrogen, cabbage yield and root growth

across five locations in Northern and Western Europe. *European Journal of Agronomy* 120, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2020.126144>

- Hlisnikovsky, L., & Kunzová, E. (2014). Effect of mineral and organic fertilizers on yield and technological parameters of winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) on illimerized Luvisol. *Polish Journal of Agronomy*, 17, 18-24.
- Hodson, M. E., Valsami-Jones, E., Cotter-Howells, J. D., Dubbin, W. E., Kemp, A. J., Thornton, I., & Warren, A. (2001). Effect of bone meal (calcium phosphate) amendments on metal release from contaminated soils: A leaching column study. *Environmental Pollution*, 112(2), 233-243.
- Horn, R., Taubner, H., Wuttke, M., & Baumgartl, T. (1994). Soil physical properties related to soil structure. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 30(2-4), 187-216.
- Imbufe, A. U., Patti, A. F., Burrow, D., Surapaneni, A., Jackson, W. R., & Milner, A. D. (2005). Effects of potassium humate on aggregate stability of two soils from Victoria, Australia. *Geoderma*, 125(3-4), 321-330.
- Iocoli, G. A., et al., (2019). Use of biogas digestates obtained by anaerobic digestion and co-digestion as fertilizers: Characterization, soil biological activity and growth dynamic of *Lactuca sativa* L. *Science of the Total Environment*, 647, 11-19.
- Irshad, M., Eneji, A. E., Hussain, Z., & Ashraf, M. (2013). Chemical characterization of fresh and composted livestock manures. *Journal of Soil Science and Plant Nutrition*, 13(1), 115-121.
- Jansson, J. K., & Baker, E. S. (2016). A multi-omic future for microbiome studies. *Nature Microbiology*, 1(5), 1-3.
- Jeffery, S., Gardi, C., Jones, A., Montanarella, L., Marmo, L., Miko, L., et al., (2010). *European Atlas of Soil Biodiversity*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- Kasparinskis, R., & Nikodemus, O. (2012). Influence of environmental factors on forest soil spatial distribution and diversity in Latvia. *Estonian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 61(1), 48-64.
- Kaufmann, M., Tobias, S., & Schulin, R. (2010). Comparison of critical limits for crop plant growth based on different indicators for the state of soil compaction. *Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science*, 173(4), 573-583.
- Kemper, W. D., & Koch, E. J. (1966). Aggregate stability of soils from Western United States and Canada: Measurement procedure, correlations with soil constituents. *Agricultural Research Service, US Department of Agriculture*, No. 1355.
- Khan, W., Rayirath, U. P., Subramanian, S., Jithesh, M. N., Rayorath, P., Hodges, D. M., ... & Prithviraj, B. (2009). Seaweed extracts as biostimulants of plant growth and development. *Journal of Plant Growth Regulation*, 28, 386-399.
- Kozák, J., Borůvka, L., & Němeček, J. (2003). Degradation of soils in the Czech Republic. *Land Degradation in Central and Eastern Europe. European Soil Bureau Research Report*, (10), 177-192.
- Lal, R. (2020). Soil organic matter and water retention. *Agronomy Journal*, 112(5), 3265-3277.
- Lavelle, P., Decaëns, T., Aubert, M., Barot, S., Blouin, M., Bureau, F., ... & Rossi, J. P. (2006). Soil invertebrates and ecosystem services. *European Journal of Soil Biology*, 42, S3-S15.

- Lavelle, P., Spain, A., Blouin, M., Brown, G., Decaëns, T., Grimaldi, M., ... & Zangerlé, A. (2016). Ecosystem engineers in a self-organized soil: A review of concepts and future research questions. *Soil Science*, 181(3/4), 91-109.
- Le Quéré, C., Moriarty, R., Andrew, R. M., Peters, G. P., Ciais, P., Friedlingstein, P., ... & Raupach, M. R. (2014). Global carbon budget 2014. *Earth System Science Data*, 7(1), 47-85.
- Ledchumanakumar, S., Aruchchunan, N., Kandiah, P., & Gunasingham, M. (2021, May). Root-knot nematode management using chitin-rich fish industry by-product in organic brinjal cultivation. In *Biology and Life Sciences Forum* (Vol. 3, No. 1, p. 57). MDPI.
- Liddle, K., McGonigle, T., & Koiter, A. (2020). Microbe biomass in relation to organic carbon and clay in soil. *Soil Systems*, 4(3), 28.
- Lim, S. L., Wu, T. Y., Lim, P. N., & Shak, K. P. Y. (2015). The use of vermicompost in organic farming: Overview, effects on soil and economics. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 95(6), 1143-1156.
- Lorenz, K., Lal, R., & Ehlers, K. (2019). Soil organic carbon stock as an indicator for monitoring land and soil degradation in relation to United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals. *Land Degradation & Development*, 30(7), 824-838.
- Lukas, V., Neudert, L., Dryšlová, T., Novák, J., Smutný, V., Křen, J. (2015). Modifikace agrochemického zkoušení půd pro variabilní aplikaci hnojiv v precizním zemědělství. Aktuální poznatky v pěstování, šlechtění, ochraně rostlin, 99.
- Magdoff, F., & Weil, R. R. (2004). Soil organic matter management strategies. In *Soil organic matter in sustainable agriculture* (pp. 97-133). CRC Press.
- Maienza, A., Baronti, S., Lanini, G. M., Ugolini, F., Ungaro, F., & Vaccari, F. P. (2022). The QBS-ar Index: A sensitive tool to assess the effectiveness of an agroecological practice in the Italian Alpine region. *Journal of Soil Science and Plant Nutrition*, 22(3), 3740-3744.
- Maienza, A., Fornasier, F., & Berti, A. (2017). Soil carbon dynamics as an indicator of the effectiveness of agroecological practices. *Ecological Indicators*, 74, 240-247.
- Malhi, S. S., Nyborg, M., Solberg, E. D., Dyck, M. F., & Puurveen, D. (2011). Improving crop yield and N uptake with long-term straw retention in two contrasting soil types. *Field Crops Research*, 124(3), 378-391.
- Marinari, S., Mancinelli, R., Campiglia, E., & Grego, S. (2006). Chemical and biological indicators of soil quality in organic and conventional farming systems in Central Italy. *Ecological Indicators*, 6(4), 701-711.
- Matthews, A. (2022). Prospects for Agroecology in Europe. *EuroChoices*, 21(3), 80-83.
- Maurya, S., Abraham, J. S., Somasundaram, S., Toteja, R., Gupta, R., & Makhija, S. (2020). Indicators for assessment of soil quality: A mini-review. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 192, 1-22.
- Mayura, K., et al. (2020). Integrating physical, chemical, and biological parameters for comprehensive soil quality assessment. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 84(5), 1346-1358.
- Meng, X., Ma, C., & Petersen, S. O. (2022). Sensitive control of N₂O emissions and microbial community dynamics by organic fertilizer and soil interactions. *Biology and Fertility of Soils*, 58(7), 771-788.

- Menta, C., Conti, F. D., & Pinto, S. (2018). Microarthropods biodiversity in natural, semi-natural, and cultivated soils—QBS-ar approach. *Applied Soil Ecology*, 123, 740-743.
- Metzger, M. J. (2005). Europe's ecological regions: Indicators for the environment. European Environment Agency.
- Metzger, M. J., Bunce, R. G. H., Jongman, R. H. G., Sayre, R., Trabucco, A., & Zomer, R. (2005). A high-resolution bioclimate map of the world: A unifying framework for global biodiversity research and monitoring. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 14(6), 565-582.
- Meurer, K., Barron, J., Chenu, C., Coucheney, E., Fielding, M., Hallett, P., ... & Jarvis, N. (2020). A framework for modeling soil structure dynamics induced by biological activity. *Global Change Biology*, 26(10), 5382-5403.
- Minasny, B., Hong, S. Y., Hartemink, A. E., Kim, Y. H., & Kang, S. S. (2016). Soil pH increase under paddy in South Korea between 2000 and 2012. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 221, 205-213.
- Mohite, B. V., & Patil, S. V. (2022). Isolation and Identification of Nonsymbiotic *Azotobacter* and Symbiotic *Azotobacter Paspali*–*Paspalum notatum*. In *Practical Handbook on Agricultural Microbiology* (pp. 25-33).
- Monard, C., Jeanneau, L., Le Garrec, J. L., Le Bris, N., Binet, F. (2020). Short-term effect of pig slurry and its digestate application on biochemical properties of soils and emissions of volatile organic compounds. *Applied Soil Ecology*, 147, 103376.
- Montgomery, D. R., Biklé, A., Archuleta, R., Brown, P., & Jordan, J. (2022). Soil health and nutrient density: Preliminary comparison of regenerative and conventional farming. *PeerJ*, 10, e12848.
- Mosa, A. A., Taha, A., & Elsaied, M. (2020). Agro-environmental applications of humic substances: A critical review. *Egyptian Journal of Soil Science*, 60(3), 211-229.
- Muller, A., Schader, C., El-Hage Scialabba, N., Brüggemann, J., Isensee, A., Erb, K. H., ... & Niggli, U. (2017). Strategies for feeding the world more sustainably with organic agriculture. *Nature Communications*, 8(1), 1-13.
- Neher, D. A. (2001). Role of nematodes in soil health and their use as indicators. *Journal of Nematology*, 33(4), 161-168.
- Neina, D. (2019). The role of soil pH in plant nutrition and soil remediation. *Applied and Environmental Soil Science*, 2019, 1-9.
- Nielsen, M. N., Winding, A., Binnerup, S., Hansen, B. M., Hendriksen, N. B., & Kroer, N. (2002). Microorganisms as indicators of soil health. Technical Report No. 388. Denmark: National Environment Research Institute.
- Nielsen, R. L., Thomison, P. R., Brown, G. A., Halter, A. L., Wells, J., & Wuethrich, K. L. (2002). Delayed planting effects on flowering and grain maturation of dent corn. *Agronomy Journal*, 94(3), 549-558.
- Nikodemus, O., Kasparinskis, R., & Kukuls, I. (2013). Influence of afforestation on soil genesis, morphology, and properties in glacial till deposits. *Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science*, 59(3), 449-465.
- Odoux, V., Bockel, L., & Tassin, J. (2022). Agroecology for large-scale farming: Addressing questions in research, technology, and policy development. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 6, 802270.

- Okalebo, J. R., Gathua, K. W., & Woomer, P. L. (2002). Laboratory methods of soil and plant analysis: A working manual (2nd ed.). Sacred Africa, Nairobi, 21, 25-26.
- Oliver, D. P., Bramley, R. G. V., Riches, D., Porter, I., & Edwards, J. (2013). Soil physical and chemical properties as indicators of soil quality in Australian viticulture. *Australian Journal of Grape and Wine Research*, 19(2), 129-137.
- Olson, K., Ebelhar, S. A., & Lang, J. M. (2014). Long-term effects of cover crops on crop yields, soil organic carbon stocks, and sequestration. *Open Journal of Soil Science*, 2014.
- O'Neill, B., Sprunger, C. D., & Robertson, G. P. (2021). Do soil health tests match farmer experience? Assessing biological, physical, and chemical indicators in the Upper Midwest United States. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 85(3), 903-918.
- Padilla, F. M., Farneselli, M., Gianquinto, G., Tei, F., & Thompson, R. B. (2020). Monitoring nitrogen status of vegetable crops and soils for optimal nitrogen management. *Agricultural Water Management*, 241, 106356.
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., ... & Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*, 372, n71.
- Pagliai, M., & De Nobili, M. (1993). Relationships between soil porosity, root development and soil enzyme activity in cultivated soils. In *Soil structure/soil biota interrelationships* (pp. 243-256). Elsevier.
- Paoletti, M. G. (1999). The role of earthworms for assessment of sustainability and as bioindicators. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 74(1-3), 137-155.
- Parisi, V., Menta, C., Gardi, C., Jacomini, C., & Mozzanica, E. (2005). Microarthropod communities as a tool to assess soil quality and biodiversity: A new approach in Italy. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 105(1-2), 323-333.
- Parmar, D. K., Thakur, D. R., & Jamwal, R. S. (2016). Effect of long-term organic manure application on soil properties, carbon sequestration, soil-plant carbon stock, and productivity under two vegetable production systems in Himachal Pradesh. *Journal of Environmental Biology*, 37, 333-339.
- Peigné, J., Ball, B. C., Roger-Estrade, J., & David, C. (2007). Is conservation tillage suitable for organic farming? A review. *Soil Use and Management*, 23(2), 129-144.
- Peiris, D., Patti, A. F., Jackson, W. R., Marshall, M., & Smith, C. J. (2002). The use of Ca-modified, brown-coal-derived humates and fulvates for treatment of soil acidity. *Soil Research*, 40(7), 1171-1186.
- Phalan, B., Green, R. E., Dicks, L. V., Dotta, G., Feniuk, C., Lamb, A., ... & Balmford, A. (2016). How can higher-yield farming help to spare nature? *Science*, 351(6272), 450-451.
- Piccolo, A., & Mbagwu, J. S. C. (1989). Effects of humic substances and surfactants on the stability of soil aggregates. *Soil science*, 147(1), 47-54.
- Piribauer, C., Knodt, R., Link, S., Engels, M., Stern, B., & Braun, N. (2020). Humic substances as additives in ceramic clays and bodies. In *Ceram. Forum Int* (Vol. 97, No. 1, pp. 36-42).
- Piwowar, A. (2022). Consumption of mineral fertilizers in Polish agriculture—Trends and directions of changes. *Agricultural Research*, 11(3), 477-487.

- Piwowar, A., & Harasym, J. (2020). The importance and prospects of the use of algae in agribusiness. *Sustainability*, 12(14), 5669.
- Post, W. M., Izaurrealde, R. C., Mann, L. K., & Bliss, N. (2001). Monitoring and verifying changes of organic carbon in soil. *Climatic Change*, 51(1), 73-99.
- Powlson, D. S., Stirling, C. M., Jat, M. L., Gerard, B. G., Palm, C. A., Sanchez, P. A., & Cassman, K. G. (2014). Limited potential of no-till agriculture for climate change mitigation. *Nature Climate Change*, 4(8), 678-683.
- Powlson, D. S., Whitmore, A. P., & Goulding, K. W. T. (2011). Soil carbon sequestration to mitigate climate change: A critical re-examination to identify the true and the false. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 62, 42-55.
- Pulido Moncada, M., Gabriels, D., Cornelis, W., & Lobo, D. (2015). Comparing aggregate stability tests for soil physical quality indicators. *Land Degradation & Development*, 26(8), 843-852.
- Rabot, E., Wiesmeier, M., Schlüter, S., & Vogel, H. J. (2018). Soil structure as an indicator of soil functions: A review. *Geoderma*, 314, 122-137.
- Raffa, D. W., Antichi, D., Carlesi, S., Puig-Sirera, A., Rallo, G., & Bàrberi, P. (2022). Ground vegetation covers increase grape yield and must quality in Mediterranean organic vineyards despite variable effects on vine water deficit and nitrogen status. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 136, 126483.
- Rahmanipour, F., Marzaioli, R., Bahrami, H. A., Fereidouni, Z., & Bandarabadi, S. R. (2014). Assessment of soil quality indices in agricultural lands of Qazvin Province, Iran. *Ecological indicators*, 40, 19-26.
- Raich, J. W., & Schlesinger, W. H. (1992). The global carbon dioxide flux in soil respiration and its relationship to vegetation and climate. *Tellus B*, 44(2), 81-99.
- Ramírez, P. B., Calderón, F. J., Fonte, S. J., & Bonilla, C. A. (2019). Environmental controls and long-term changes on carbon stocks under agricultural lands. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 186, 310-321.
- Ramos, F. T., Dores, E. F. D. C., Weber, O. L. D. S., Beber, D. C., Campelo Jr, J. H., & Maia, J. C. D. S. (2018). Soil organic matter doubles the cation exchange capacity of tropical soil under no-till farming in Brazil. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 98(9), 3595-3602.
- Rawlins, B. G., Turner, G., Wragg, J., McLachlan, P., & Lark, R. M. (2015). An improved method for measurement of soil aggregate stability using laser granulometry applied at regional scale. *European Journal of Soil Science*, 66(3), 604-614.
- Rayment, G. E., & Lyons, D. J. (2011). *Soil chemical methods: Australasia (Vol. 3)*. CSIRO publishing.
- Razzaghi, F., Obour, P. B., & Arthur, E. (2020). Does biochar improve soil water retention? A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Geoderma*, 361, 114055.
- Rezaei, S. A., Gilkes, R. J., & Andrews, S. S. (2006). A minimum data set for assessing soil quality in rangelands. *Geoderma*, 136(1-2), 229-234.
- Ruano-Rosa, D., & Mercado-Blanco, J. (2015). Combining biocontrol agents and organics amendments to manage soil-borne phytopathogens. In *Organic amendments and soil suppressiveness in plant disease management* (pp. 457-478).

- Rusakova, E., Sukhacheva, E., & Hartemink, A. E. (2022). Vasilii Dokuchaev: A biographical sketch on the occasion of his 175th birthday. *Geoderma*, 412, 115718.
- Sainz-Rozas, H. R., Echeverría, H. E., & Barbieri, P. A. (2004). Nitrogen balance as affected by application time and nitrogen fertilizer rate in irrigated no-tillage maize. *Agronomy Journal*, 96(6), 1622-1631.
- Schloter, M., Nannipieri, P., Sørensen, S. J., & van Elsas, J. D. (2018). Microbial indicators for soil quality. *Biology and Fertility of Soils*, 54(1), 1-10.
- Schlüter, S., Großmann, C., Diel, J., Wu, G. M., Tischer, S., Deubel, A., & Rücknagel, J. (2018). Long-term effects of conventional and reduced tillage on soil structure, soil ecological and soil hydraulic properties. *Geoderma*, 332, 10-19.
- Schollenberger, C. J. (1945). Determination of soil organic matter. *Soil Science*, 59(1), 53-56.
- Scott, H. D., Wood, L. S., & Miley, W. N. (1986). Long-term effects of tillage on the retention and transport of soil water. *Transactions of the ASAE*, 29(4), 1093-1097.
- Senesi, N., Rizzi, F. R., Dellino, P., & Acquafredda, P. (1997). Fractal humic acids in aqueous suspensions at various concentrations, ionic strengths, and pH values. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, 127(1-3), 57-68.
- Seufert, V., Ramankutty, N., & Foley, J. A. (2012). Comparing the yields of organic and conventional agriculture. *Nature*, 485(7397), 229-232.
- Seybold, C. A., Mansbach, M. J., Karlen, D. L., & Rogers, H. H. (2018). Quantification of soil quality. In *Soil Processes and the Carbon Cycle* (pp. 387-404). CRC Press.
- Sharma, P., Singh, A., Kahlon, C. S., Brar, A. S., Grover, K. K., Dia, M., & Steiner, R. L. (2018). The role of cover crops towards sustainable soil health and agriculture—A review paper. *American Journal of Plant Sciences*, 9(9), 1935-1951.
- Shvets, O. (2022). Variety and action of soil microorganisms in diverse Ukraine climatic zones. *Revista Amazonia Investiga*, 11(55), 256-264.
- Siddaway, A. P., Wood, A. M., & Hedges, L. V. (2019). How to do a systematic review: A best practice guide for conducting and reporting narrative reviews, meta-analyses, and meta-syntheses. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 70(1), 747-770.
- Smith, J. L., & Doran, J. W. (1997). Measurement and use of pH and electrical conductivity for soil quality analysis. *Methods for assessing soil quality*, 49, 169-185.
- Smith, P., Powlson, D., Glendining, M., & Smith, J. O. (1997). Potential for carbon sequestration in European soils: preliminary estimates for five scenarios using results from long-term experiments. *Global Change Biology*, 3(1), 67-79.
- Snapp, S. S., Swinton, S. M., Labarta, R., Mutch, D., Black, J. R., Leep, R., ... & O'Neil, K. (2005). Evaluating cover crops for benefits, costs, and performance within cropping system niches. *Agronomy Journal*, 97(1), 322-332.
- Song, M., Jing, S., Zhou, Y., Hui, Y., Zhu, L., Wang, F., ... & Wan, S. (2015). Dynamics of soil nematode communities in wheat fields under different nitrogen management in Northern China Plain. *European Journal of Soil Biology*, 71, 13-20.
- Sosna, I., & Fudali, E. (2023). Usefulness of living mulch in rows in a dwarf pear, *Pyrus communis* L., orchard. *Agriculture*, 13(11), 2145.

- Steenhoudt O., Vanderleyden J. (2000). Azospirillum , a free-living nitrogen-fixing bacterium closely associated with grasses: genetic, biochemical and ecological aspects. *FEMS Microbiology Reviews*. 24(4), 487-506.
- Stockmann, U., Padarian, J., McBratney, A., Minasny, B., de Brogniez, D., Montanarella, L., ... & Field, D. J. (2015). Global soil organic carbon assessment. *Global Food Security*, 6, 9-16.
- Stolte, J., Tesfai, M., Øygarden, L., Kværnø, S., Keizer, J., Verheijen, F., ... & Hessel, R. (Eds.). (2015). *Soil threats in Europe*. Luxembourg: Publications Office.
- Stork, N. E. (1995). Measuring and inventorying arthropod diversity in temperate and tropical forests. In *IUFRO Symposium*, Chiang Mai, Thailand.
- Sullivan, P. (2002). Drought resistant soil. ATTRA (Appropriate Technology Transfer for Rural Areas), National Center for Appropriate Technology. Retrieved from http://agwaterstewards.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/Drought_Resistant_Soils_ATTRA.pdf
- Tan, K. H., & Binger, A. (1986). Effect of humic acid on aluminum toxicity in corn plants. *Soil Science*, 141(1), 20-25.
- Tisdall, J. M., & Oades, J. M. (1982). Organic matter and water-stable aggregates in soils. *Journal of soil science*, 33(2), 141-163.
- Tittonell, P., Piñeiro, G., Garibaldi, L. A., Dogliotti, S., Olf, H., & Jobbagy, E. G. (2020). Agroecology in large scale farming – A research agenda. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 4, 214.
- Topa, D., Cara, I. G., & Jitoreanu, G. (2021). Long-term impact of different tillage systems on carbon pools and stocks, soil bulk density, aggregation, and nutrients: A field meta-analysis. *Catena*, 199, 105102.
- Tu, C., Ristaino, J. B., & Hu, S. (2006). Soil microbial biomass and activity in organic tomato farming systems: Effects of organic inputs and straw mulching. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 38, 247-255.
- Ungaro, F., Maienza, A., Ugolini, F., Lanini, G. M., Baronti, S., & Calzolari, C. (2022). Assessment of joint soil ecosystem services supply in urban green spaces: A case study in Northern Italy. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 67, 127455.
- Usharani, K. V., Roopashree, K. M., & Naik, D. (2019). Role of soil physical, chemical and biological properties for soil health improvement and sustainable agriculture. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*, 8(5), 1256-1267.
- Valpassos, M. A. R., Cavalcante, E. G. S., Cassiolato, A. M. R., & Alves, M. C. (2001). Effects of soil management systems on soil microbial activity, bulk density, and chemical properties. *Pesquisa Agropecuária Brasileira*, 36, 1539-1545.
- van Bruggen, A. H., He, M. M., Shin, K., Mai, V., Jeong, K. C., Finckh, M. R., & Morris Jr, J. G. (2018). Environmental and health effects of the herbicide glyphosate. *Science of the Total Environment*, 616, 255-268.
- Van der Ploeg, J. D., Franco, J., & Renting, H. (2019). Agroecological systems and the paradigm shift in agriculture. *Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems*, 43(12), 1359-1379.
- van Groenigen, J. W., Lubbers, I. M., Vos, H. M., Brown, G. G., De Deyn, G. B., & van Groenigen, K. J. (2014). Earthworms increase plant production: A meta-analysis. *Scientific Reports*, 4(1), 6365.

- van Midden, C., Harris, J., Shaw, L., Sizmur, T., & Pawlett, M. (2023). The impact of anaerobic digestate on soil life: A review. *Applied Soil Ecology*, 191, 105066.
- Vicente-Vicente, J. L., García-Ruiz, R., Aranda, V., & Calero, J. (2015, March). E4/E6 ratio measured by UV-VIS spectroscopy as an indicator of soil organic matter quality in Andalusian olive groves. In Conference: VII Jornadas Jóvenes Investigadores en Física Atómica y Molecular, Jaén, Spain.
- Wagg, C., et al. (2014). Soil biodiversity and soil community composition determine ecosystem multifunctionality. *PNAS* v. 111, 5266-5270.
- Wang, Y., Hu, N., Xu, M., Li, Z., Lou, Y., Chen, Y., ... & Wang, Z. L. (2015). 23-year manure and fertilizer application increases soil organic carbon sequestration of a rice-barley cropping system. *Biology and Fertility of Soils*, 51, 583-591.
- Wardle, D. A., & Ghani, A. (1995). Why is the strength of relationships between pairs of methods for estimating soil microbial biomass often so variable? *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 27(6), 821-828.
- Wezel, A., Soboksa, G., McClelland, S., Delespesse, F., & Boissau, A. (2015). The blurred boundaries of ecological, sustainable, and agroecological intensification: A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 35, 1283-1295.
- Wiesmeier, M., Urbanski, L., Hobley, E., Lang, B., von Lützow, M., Marin-Spiotta, E., ... & Kögel-Knabner, I. (2019). Soil organic carbon storage as a key function of soils-A review of drivers and indicators at various scales. *Geoderma*, 333, 149-162.
- Wollny, W. (1898). Untersuchungen über den Einfluß der Luftfeuchtigkeit auf das Wachstum der Pflanzen. *Forschungen auf dem Gebiete der Agrikulturphysik*, Bd. XX, p. 528.
- Wortman, S. E., Francis, C. A., Bernards, M. L., Drijber, R. A., & Lindquist, J. L. (2012). Optimizing cover crop benefits with diverse mixtures and an alternative termination method. *Agronomy Journal*, 104(5), 1425-1435.
- Wurst, S., Sonnemann, I., & Zaller, J. G. (2018). Soil macro-invertebrates: Their impact on plants and associated aboveground communities in temperate regions. In *Aboveground-Belowground Community Ecology* (pp. 175-200).
- Xu, Q., Ling, N., Chen, H., Duan, Y., Wang, S., Shen, Q., ... & Kent, A. D. (2020). Long-term chemical-only fertilization induces a diversity decline and deep selection on the soil bacteria. *MSystems*, 5(4), e00667-20.
- Yan, S., Singh, A. N., Fu, S., Liao, C., Wang, S., Li, Y., ... & Hu, L. (2012). A soil fauna index for assessing soil quality. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*, 47, 158-165.
- Yang, F., Tang, C., & Antonietti, M. (2021). Natural and artificial humic substances to manage minerals, ions, water, and soil microorganisms. *Chemical Society Reviews*, 50(10), 6221-6239.
- Yao, R., Yang, J., Gao, P., Zhang, J., & Jin, W. (2013). Determining minimum data set for soil quality assessment of typical salt-affected farmland in the coastal reclamation area. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 128, 137-145.
- Young, R. (2012). *Soil properties and behaviour* (Vol. 5). Elsevier.
- Yu, P., Liu, S., Zhang, L., Li, Q., & Zhou, D. (2018). Selecting the minimum data set and quantitative soil quality indexing of alkaline soils under different land uses in northeastern China. *Science of The Total Environment*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.10.301>

- Zhang, W., Qiao, W., Gao, D., Dai, Y., Deng, J., Yang, G., ... & Ren, G. (2018). Relationship between soil nutrient properties and biological activities along a restoration chronosequence of *Pinus tabulaeformis* plantation forests in the Ziwuling Mountains, China. *Catena*, 161, 85-95.
- Zhao, Y., Zhang, R., Jiang, K. W., Qi, J., Hu, Y., Guo, J., ... & Ma, H. (2021). Nuclear phylotranscriptomics and phylogenomics support numerous polyploidization events and hypotheses for the evolution of rhizobial nitrogen-fixing symbiosis in Fabaceae. *Molecular Plant*, 14(5), 748-773.
- Zuazo, V. H. D., & Pleguezuelo, C. R. R. (2009). Soil-erosion and runoff prevention by plant covers: A review. In *Sustainable Agriculture* (pp. 785-811).